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CRAFTING THE FUTURE: A
STUDY ON THE IMPACT OF
INTELLIGENT CV TOOLS AND
ASSESSING THE ROLE OF AI IN
IT CAREER PATH AND
PROFESSIONAL ADVISING

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Abstract

This research paper introduces an innovative AI-driven career guidance solution for the IT industry with other AI features and CV generation. Transitioning from academics to the professional world presents many important hurdles for recent graduates in the ever-growing and dynamic IT business. The project's results offer a fresh perspective on career development in the quickly expanding IT industry, which makes a substantial contribution to the area.

The main part of the predictive feature is developing and evaluating various machine learning models. The RandomForestClassifier was ultimately chosen for its high accuracy and robustness. Complementing this, the platform boasts a user-friendly interface, enabling users to create customized CVs, enriched with AI-based advice on relevant skills and qualifications.

Comprehensive testing strategies, including unit, user acceptance, and integration tests, were employed to ensure the reliability of the software and user satisfaction. The backend, developed in Python, was hosted on Render, while the frontend was deployed on Vercel, ensuring a smooth user experience. A strong emphasis was also placed on data privacy and ethical compliance.

The results, derived from extensive testing and user feedback, demonstrated the platform's effectiveness in offering precise career guidance and facilitating the creation of professional, personalized CVs. The success of this project transcends its technical achievements, highlighting its potential to reshape career development in the IT industry.

Conclusively, this research makes a substantial contribution to the field of AI applications in professional development. It illustrates the powerful synergy of AI and user-centered design, potentially inspiring future innovations in career advisory tools. This study provides essential insights into leveraging machine learning for practical, real-world applications, guiding future efforts in AI-driven career services.

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Acronyms and Abbreviations

Artificial Intelligence (AI)

Curriculum Vitae (CV)

Machine Learning (ML)

Random Forest Classifier (RFC)

Support Vector Machine (SVM)

K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN)

Natural Language Processing (NLP)

Natural Language Generation (NLG)

Applicant Tracking Systems (ATS)

General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR)

Unified Modeling Language (UML)

Entity Relationship Diagram (ERD)

Data Flow Diagram (DFD)

Human Resource Management (HRM)

Information Technology (IT)

Empirical Research Method (ERM)

OpenAI's GPT-3.5 Turbo (GPT-3.5 Turbo)

JavaScript Object Notation (JSON)

Cross-Validation (CV)

HyperText Markup Language (HTML)

Cascading Style Sheets (CSS)

Introduction

The research paper begins by acknowledging the transformative role of Information Technology in the Global Economy and its impact on job market dynamics, encapsulated within the research theme "Crafting the Future: A Study on the Impact of Intelligent CV Tools and Assessing the Role of AI in IT Career Path and Professional Advising". This seeks to examine and understand the crucial function of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in determining career routes and the process of job application within the IT sector. This research was also conducted in Sri Lanka, a nation where the job market gets updated rapidly.

This research was sparked by a market gap in personalized AI tools for CV generation and career guidance, particularly for IT professionals. While there are numerous CV-building tools available, they often fail to provide comprehensive career advice. The objective of this paper is to evaluate the effectiveness of AI-driven tools in assisting IT professionals and graduates with both CV creation and career guidance. Despite the abundance of CV tools, there remains a gap in their ability to cater to the unique needs of IT professionals. Our study aims to delve deeper into this gap and assess how AI can be utilized to provide tailored and efficient career advising.

In the contemporary job market, especially within the IT industry, a well-crafted CV is more than a mere summary of skills, it's a key instrument for professional advancement. Also due to the quick growth of technology, there are various job choices to pick from especially when it comes to the IT field.

Problem Statement

The primary objective of this research study is to address the shortcomings of existing platforms for career counseling and CV creation, with a focus on the IT industry. While there are numerous solutions available in the market, they often fall short of meeting the complex and specific requirements of workers, resulting in generic outputs that do not cater to their evolving needs. Also with the rapidly evolving IT industry, almost all the fresh graduates and beginners to the IT industry are often confused on which career path they should pursue. Also when it comes to career advising, recommended skills and qualifications, many people don't have an idea on actually what they should possess and develop.

This disparity is even more pronounced in Sri Lanka, where local offerings for such platforms are nonexistent or rare. Consequently, IT professionals with impeccable credentials often struggle to navigate the vast sea of job options and identify the best match for their goals and skills. This research aims to propose innovative solutions that can cater to the unique requirements of the IT industry, help professionals make informed career choices as well as give suitable career advice, required skill sets and qualifications for all.

The project will explore how AI-driven platforms can offer more than simply CV-building; they can become career consultants, aligning with the competencies and ambitions of individuals. The study will analyze the current landscape of such technologies, their usefulness, and the future potential they contain. The study intends to bridge the existing market gap by integrating AI-driven models to provide real-time career path ideas and guidance, thereby changing the future of recruitment and career development in IT.

Research Question

The research question that guides this study is: How can the integration of AI and machine learning techniques enhance career path guidance for fresh graduates and job seekers in the IT Sector and generate a CV?

Comparison with Existing Tools

In contrast of other conventional CV generators, this project gives extra features such as AI-Driven career recommendation when it comes to the IT sector, career advising, skill recommendations and qualification/certification guidance for various job roles in different sectors. A notable feature is the mock interview module, which not only prepares candidates for interviews but also provides constructive feedback a functionality absent in current market offerings.

The application being discussed in this context boasts several unique features, which distinguish it from other existing tools:

1. **Predictive Career Analysis for IT Industry:** Unlike other tools, it can predict potential IT careers based on the skills and knowledge on certain skills, offering a level of personalization and foresight unmatched by existing products.
2. **Comprehensive Career Advice:** It extends beyond CV building to offer strategic career advice based on job roles. This feature supports any kind of job as well as in any industry at any level. This is a feature especially lacking in the Sri Lankan context.
3. **Skill and Qualification Guidance:** The platform recommends skills and qualifications pertinent to chosen career paths, ensuring users are well-equipped to meet industry standards.
4. **Mock Interview Feature:** This innovative component simulates real-world interviews, providing users with invaluable practice and feedback, thereby enhancing their interview preparedness.

The dearth of sophisticated career guidance tools in Sri Lanka has been a pressing concern, and this research offers a promising solution that not only addresses the issue but also represents an innovative approach. This study holds particular significance in the context of Sri Lanka, given that it caters to a critical need in the country's IT job market. It is anticipated that the development of this tool will establish a new standard in career advisory services in the region, providing novel insights and functionalities that are not currently available.

Conclusion

Moreover, this research aims to make significant contributions to both the IT and AI fields. By showcasing the potential of AI in transforming the domain of career guidance and professional development, it endeavors to offer novel perspectives and insights into the subject matter. This research will also help people who are relatively new to the IT field and fresh graduates to start their career. Additionally, by focusing on the IT sector, particularly in a developing IT landscape, this study provides unique insights into how AI can be leveraged to enhance career recommendations and career development tools and address specific market needs.

In conclusion, this article attempts to provide a comprehensive knowledge of the role of AI in career advising, stressing its potential to alter the IT job market and the way professionals approach their career development. Through this investigation, the article hopes to give significant insights to both the discipline of IT and the expanding realm of AI applications in professional development.

Literature Review

Introduction

Career guidance systems have been instrumental in helping individuals navigate the complex landscape of career opportunities. With the emergence of artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning (ML), these systems have undergone a transformative shift, offering unprecedented precision and personalization in career recommendations. This literature review aims to explore the integration of AI and ML into career guidance systems, focusing on the transformative potential and the multifaceted approaches adopted in recent research. The selected studies encapsulate a range of perspectives, from predictive analytics and personality assessment to the nuanced challenges of resume content generation and job matching. Through this review, we aim to provide a comprehensive overview of the state-of-the-art AI-driven career guidance systems, highlighting the advancements and ongoing challenges in the field.

Literature Review

Career Guidance System Using Machine Learning (Subiddhya Panthee, 2023) ([1DOI](#))

Subiddhya Panthee's 2023 research represents a significant contribution when it comes to the field of career guidance, demonstrating the ability of machine learning to deliver personalized career recommendations. By integrating psychological assessments—namely the Big Five personality test and the VAK learning styles—with ML algorithms, the research advances a nuanced approach to career counseling.

The study is notable for using various ML techniques. The use of RandomForest and SVM algorithms, chosen for their respective accuracy rates of 91.14% and 90.50%, underscores the precision when it comes to career guidance. The attention to data pre-processing further establishes the reliability of the input data, ensuring that the algorithms' performance is based on high-quality information.

Performance analysis was done via confusion matrix in this research, providing a transparent assessment of the classifiers' accuracy. The matrices showed how well the models could predict, with very few mistakes. This level of accuracy is very relevant in the context of career guidance, where the cost of an incorrect recommendation can have substantial implications for an individual's career trajectory.

The research by Panthee has broad implications for the role of AI-driven tools in career counseling. Due to the rapid growth of the IT sector, the demand for sophisticated career guidance systems that can handle a complex array of data and deliver tailored recommendations becomes increasingly vital. Panthee's study suggests that machine learning algorithms can significantly enhance the capabilities of these systems, offering a level of personalization and accuracy that traditional methods may not be able to achieve.

In conclusion, Panthee's research clearly shows that machine learning algorithms have an important role to play in the future of business strategy. The findings of this study contribute valuable insights into more sophisticated data-driven career counseling tools that can provide tailored recommendations that can help bridge the gap between job seekers and their ideal career paths.

An Intelligent Career Guidance System using Machine Learning (Vignesh S, 2021) ([2DOI](#))

Vignesh S's recent study introduces an Intelligent Career Guidance System that addresses the complex decision-making process where the students face during a crucial point in their educational journey. This research indicates that during age of 18, a lack of direction and experience often leads to hasty and uninformed career choices. This proves how important my research will influence the real world. What sets this system apart is its objective evaluation of a student's abilities, which is then used to recommend potential tertiary education paths.

Vignesh's research follows a comprehensive methodology, analyzing core and sub-skills and mapping them against various engineering disciplines. The system is not limited to primary recommendations but also offers secondary and tertiary suggestions, opening opportunities for students to explore different avenues that align with their competencies. This clearly aligns with my artifact since, the artifact will produce the top 3 career suggestions based on the users' skills.

The prediction module is a vital part of the system, utilizing the highly accurate K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN) algorithm. With an accuracy rate of over 90%, KNN is a dependable tool for categorizing students into various engineering departments based on their skill sets. Vignesh's research holds immense potential for career guidance and should not be overlooked. The paper reveals the power of machine learning in career counseling, especially for students transitioning into higher education. It showcases how combining skill assessment with ML predictions can provide a well-rounded analysis of suitable career opportunities.

In conclusion, the Intelligent Career Guidance System developed by Vignesh S serves as evidence of the power of AI and ML in career counseling. With its approach to career guidance, it proves that AI is a valuable tool in guiding students towards fulfilling and compatible careers.

Artificial Intelligence for Career Guidance – Current Requirements and Prospects for the Future (Stina Westman, 2021)

In her 2021 paper, Stina Westman examines the use of AI in career counseling and its potential to streamline the career advising process. The study addresses the challenges faced by youths, such as an overwhelming number of career options and resulting indecision due to a lack of experience.

Westman's research delves into the benefits and potential pitfalls of incorporating AI into career guidance, including important factors like privacy issues, data reliability, and the possibility of AI taking over human involvement. Such considerations are crucial in comprehending the ethical and real-world impacts of integrating AI into critical areas like career decision-making.

The study concludes by recognizing the potential of AI in career counseling but emphasizes that the most effective career guidance systems will likely be those that strike a balance between human insight and AI's analytical capabilities. This approach ensures that career advisories are not only data-driven but also empathetic and contextually aware, meeting the complex needs of individuals.

Westman's research has direct consequences for the current study when it comes to implementing AI systems carefully. It serves as a reminder that while AI has the potential to significantly enhance career guidance services, the human element must remain central to the process.

Westman envisions a future where AI works hand in hand with human career advisors, enhancing their guidance with advanced technology while also maintaining a fundamental human touch.

AI based Suitability Measurement and Prediction between Job Description and Job Seeker Profiles (Sridevi G, 2022) ([3DOI](#))

In today's job market, the overwhelming number of job postings online can make finding the right candidate feel like an insurmountable task. Sridevi G's recent study (2022) investigates the potential of AI in Human Resource Management (HRM), specially when it comes to matching job descriptions (JDs) with candidate resumes (CRs). The potential of artificial intelligence (AI) in human resource management (HRM) is examined in a recent study by Sridevi G (2022), particularly in relation to the matching of candidate resumes (CRs) and job descriptions (JDs). The dynamic interplay between HRM issues and AI possibilities is clarified by Sridevi. Her investigation makes clear how AI is transforming HRM procedures including hiring, onboarding, development, and retention. For instance, using Artificial Intelligence (AI) techniques such as Genetic Algorithms (GA) dramatically improves the accuracy of job-candidate matches, while the application of Natural Language Processing (NLP) greatly streamlines the recruiting process by automatically completing application forms.

Even with these developments, Sridevi admits that there is still a long way to go before the qualitative content of CRs and JDs can be fully utilized. Therefore, the goal of her research is to use machine learning (ML) approaches to forecast a candidate's eligibility and to establish a quantifiable measurement of the match between a CR and JD. This demonstrates the significance of AI.

All things considered; Sridevi's research emphasizes how crucial AI can be to modernizing HRM. Her work highlights the significance of utilizing AI to improve the accuracy and effectiveness of HRM procedures by offering a thorough examination of the technology's possible advantages and drawbacks in the hiring process.

Based on the application of AI technology in resume analysis and job recommendation (Yi-Chi Chou, 2020) ([4DOI](#))

In 2020, Yi-Chi Chou, has conducted a study exploring the use of AI technology for analyzing resumes and recommending jobs at large job fairs. This research is relevant due to the overwhelming volume of applicants that both job seekers and companies face. Chou highlights the significance of cultural fit for millennials and adopts a dual perspective, considering the perspectives of recruiters and job applicants. The study makes use of big data analytics, text mining, and machine learning to help it traverse the intricacies of online job discussions and offer tailored recommendations.

To increase the efficacy of job searching, the research approach discusses recommendation systems, such as content-based recommendation, collaborative filtering, and hybrid recommendation. Chou also emphasizes how big data makes it possible to quantify personal data and helps people advance in particular industries.

In conclusion, Chou's study utilizes AI and big data to optimize the recruitment process by providing a tailored job suggestion system for applicants and a curated list of potential candidates for companies.

This research paper proves that Artificial Intelligence has the potential to revolutionize the recruitment landscape, making it more streamlined, precise, and beneficial for all stakeholders involved.

Job Tailored Resume Content Generation (Sumedh S. Kale, 2023) ([5DOI!](#))

In a 2023 publication, Sumedh S. Kale delves into the impact of digitalization on recruitment, specifically exploring how resumes can be optimized to effectively match job descriptions. The study highlights the increasing significance of Natural Language Generation (NLG) in generating tailored resume content, particularly considering the growing prevalence of Applicant Tracking Systems (ATS) in hiring practices.

Kale acknowledges the benefits of employing specialized language models that have been trained on domain-specific data, such as IT or healthcare, which can enhance accuracy and relevance. He also addresses the challenges posed by varying resume formats and structures, as well as the limitations of current parsing tools. This research showed me how various resume templates or formats play a specific role which led me to create a CV generator which does not focus much into visuals but support more into ATS Technology.

In a compelling finale, this paper offers an ingenious outlook on the potential transformation of the resume writing process through the incorporation of Natural Language Grammar (NLG) and Natural Language Processing (NLP). By utilizing cutting-edge AI techniques to align resumes with job requirements, job seekers are afforded a distinct edge, enabling them to effectively showcase their qualifications.

Student Career Prediction Using Machine Learning (Umesh Kumar Sah, 2022)

Umesh Kumar Sah's 2022 research examines the use of machine learning (ML) to help students make informed decisions about career paths. The study looks at how well ML algorithms such as Decision Tree, Random Forest, Support Vector Machine, and Adaboost predict academic and career strategies to overcome problems of academic disconnect and job uncertainty role.

The author draws on excellent studies from the past 20 years that have used student data to predict academic achievement as a reference point for his own research. His research has a solid foundation as a result of this body of work, which includes identifying at-risk students based on characteristics such as school attendance, behavior and grades.

The research highlights the complexities of navigating various career paths and proves how important it is to empower students with the information they need to make informed choices based on their interests and skills. Umesh's work demonstrates the immense potential of ML to revolutionize career guidance and encourages further exploration of refined algorithms to improve the accuracy of career predictions.

Synthesis and Comparative Analysis

The collective analysis of the literature presents a promising direction towards integrating AI and machine learning in career guidance/prediction. The studies, though employing various kinds of methodologies, converge on the potential of AI to provide personalized and data-driven career advice.

For instance, Panthee's use of RandomForest and SVM algorithms emphasizes the accuracy and adaptability of AI in career prediction, aligning closely with the research objectives in developing an AI-driven career recommendation system. In my developed artifact, the decision to utilize RandomForest was made after comparing various models.

Similarly, Vignesh's approach to evaluating student abilities for career guidance complements the project's aim to offer tailored career suggestions. Based on this analysis, the career prediction is designed to be based on the skills & abilities of the IT students, IT fresh graduates or people who are working on the IT domain.

But, various ethical considerations and human interaction within these AI systems present a range of approaches, ranging from fully automated systems to those that blend AI with human expertise.

Future Research Directions

In the ever-changing landscape of career counseling, researchers must delve into the ethical considerations surrounding AI. Specifically, we must explore the potential impact on data privacy and address potential biases in algorithmic decision-making. Additionally, the rise of adaptable AI systems, capable of adapting to evolving employment trends and personal career progressions, is gaining traction. Exciting advancements in this field may involve the development of AI utilizing continuous learning algorithms, continuously fine-tuning to the unique needs and feedback of individual users.

My AI career prediction currently focuses exclusively on the IT sector. Expanding to more fields presents a significant challenge due to the vast number of sectors and job types involved.

Critical Analysis

While the reviewed studies demonstrate the efficacy of AI in career guidance, they also underscore challenges such as the need for extensive data preprocessing and the risk of over-reliance on algorithmic decision-making. The importance of balancing AI recommendations with human judgment and personalized advising is a recurring theme, suggesting that AI should augment rather than replace human career counselors.

AI-based systems face a recurring challenge regarding the reliability and representativeness of the data they rely on. The efficacy of machine learning models, as demonstrated in studies by Panthee and Vignesh, is dependent on the quality of the data used to train them. However, potential biases in this data can skew recommendations and have disproportionate effects on specific user groups.

The integration of AI in career guidance raises ethical concerns, particularly around data privacy and security. Personal information is often required for AI systems to function, and how this data is handled

and used is of ethical importance. While Westman's study touches on these issues, a more comprehensive exploration is necessary, especially as AI systems become more prevalent and advanced.

Advancements in AI-driven career guidance systems must consider not only the technological aspects but also the socio-economic obstacles to access. While studies provide valuable insights into the immediate effectiveness of AI in career guidance, there is less emphasis on the long-term impact of these recommendations on individuals' career trajectories. Moreover, the adaptability of AI systems to rapidly changing job markets and individual career developments remains an area for further investigation.

In this research these critical insights made it more valuable. The project aims to not only harness the power of AI for personalized career recommendations but also will be addressing the ethical, privacy concerns thereby contributing to the development of more equitable and a responsible AI driven career guidance system.

Direct Relatability to Current Research

The insights gleaned from this comprehensive literature review have played a pivotal role in shaping the present project, specifically in the selection of machine learning models and the significance of custom-tailored career suggestions. The studies' observations on issues such as ethical AI implementation and efficient data handling have also been highly influential in guiding the methodology and strategy of the ongoing research. In particular, the project's emphasis on designing a user-centric experience and maintaining ethical AI practices is in line with the wider trends and obstacles identified in the literature.

Conclusion

In conclusion, this literature review underscores the transformative impact of AI and ML in career guidance, offering insights into both the potential and challenges of these technologies. As the field continues to evolve, the need for ethical, adaptable, and user-centric AI systems becomes increasingly apparent. This research contributes to this evolving landscape by developing a solution that not only leverages AI for career recommendations but also prioritizes user privacy and ethical considerations. The findings and methodologies from the reviewed studies have been contributory in guiding the development of a more nuanced, ethical, and effective career guidance tool, paving the way for future innovations in the domain of AI-assisted career development.

Project Specification & Requirements

When developing this system, it was important to establish clear project specifications and requirements. The below section outlines and justifies the facts made in relation both functional and non-functional aspects of the project as well as other requirements.

Functional Requirements

1. **AI-Driven IT Career Recommendations:** Central to our project was the ability to predict and suggest top 3 suitable career roles in the IT domain by using AI, which works with a trained model based on a large dataset. The system should analyze users entered skills in the career recommendation page and suggest career paths and job roles which align with their skills and experiences.
2. **Dynamic CV Generation:** The tool must generate customizable CVs tailored with multiple templates. This includes various templates and the ability to incorporate specific skill sets and qualifications.
3. **Career recommendation User Interaction and Feedback:** An interactive user interface was necessary for collecting user data and providing career recommendations. The system should also be capable of receiving and processing user feedback for continuous improvement.
4. **Data Security and Privacy:** Considering we're dealing with personal user data, security measures to protect user privacy and data confidentiality are critical. No data is stored from the user.
5. **AI Suggestion UI:** An interactive user interface was necessary to collect users job role in order to provide career advising, suitable & necessary skills for the role and the recommended certifications/qualifications.

Non-Functional Requirements:

1. **Performance:** The system should perform efficiently, with minimal lag in processing user requests and generating CVs or career suggestions.
2. **Scalability:** As user numbers grow, the system should be scalable to handle increased data volumes and user interactions without a compromise in performance.
3. **Usability:** There should be a user-friendly interface, catering to a diverse range of users, with those with minimal technological expertise.
4. **Reliability:** The system must be reliable, with minimal downtime and the capability to recover quickly from potential failures.

Platform Support and Compatibility:

1. **Web-Based Platform:** The system was designed as a web-based platform to increase accessibility. This guarantees compatibility with hardware and operating systems, enabling desktop, laptop, and mobile device users to use the service.

2. **Browser Compatibility:** To guarantee that a wide range of users may access the system without any problems, the platform was made to be compatible with common web browsers like Microsoft Edge, Google Chrome, Safari and more.

Performance Requirements:

1. **Response Time:** The system was optimized for a quick response time, when generating CVs, processing career recommendations and other AI suggestions to enhance user experience.
2. **Data Processing Efficiency:** Efficient algorithms were implemented for data processing to ensure the system could handle complex computations without significant delays.

Justification of Key Decisions:

- Our selection to concentrate on AI-based career suggestions was motivated by the need for customized career guidance in the IT industry, which is currently not being addressed by existing market offerings.
- Our choice to develop a web-based platform was made to ensure that it is widely accessible and user-friendly, catering to users with varying degrees of technical expertise.
- We placed a strong emphasis on safeguarding sensitive personal and professional information by prioritizing data security and privacy.
- We prioritized performance and scalability to ensure that the tool remains efficient and effective as the number of users increases.

Tools, Frameworks, Platforms, and Software

AI Integration: For the integration of machine learning and AI, Jupyter Notebook was my preferred choice due to its flexibility in handling data preprocessing, model training, validation, and testing. Python, along with other modules, served as the foundation for coding and modeling efforts.

Frontend Design: The front-end interface was thoughtfully crafted using HTML, CSS, and JavaScript to ensure a user-friendly and responsive design. The project was developed using the latest web development technologies and frameworks to provide a seamless and interactive user experience, which is crucial for engaging modern web users.

Tools Used: To develop the code, I utilized VS Code, hosted the frontend website on Vercel, and deployed the model's backend using Render.

System Prerequisites and Accessibility

In this section of my research paper, we will be addressing the essential hardware and software requirements necessary for the optimal functioning of the Resume AI 360 system.

Hardware Requirements: Standard computing devices such as desktops, laptops, tablets, and smartphones can access the platform. It's a must to have a working internet connection to use the web-based platform.

Software Requirements: The platform is designed to be compatible with modern web browsers. These browsers must be set up to accept cookies and have JavaScript enabled to work properly. This guarantees that user sessions are efficiently managed and that all interactive aspects of the platform operate without a hitch.

Methodology

In refining the methodology section of my research paper, I combined both quantitative and qualitative approaches:

Quantitative Approach:

The participant selection for the survey involved distributing it among university colleagues, friends, and coworkers in the IT field, particularly those who are recent graduates or have just secured their first job.

To extend the participant pool, the survey was also shared via LinkedIn. This technique ensures a varied spectrum of perspectives from individuals at different stages of their IT careers. The anonymous data-gathering approach, mentioned throughout the survey, guarantees ethical standards are upheld, protecting participants' privacy and confidentiality.

For the data analysis part, I will be using Microsoft Forms, a built-in statistical tool that provides efficient means to evaluate and understand the survey data by showing it graphically. I have also used Power BI to generate few visuals for better decision making and understanding.

Research on Intelligent CV Tools & AI's Role in IT Career Advising: Shaping the Future

Figure 1 CV Research

Survey Results

The comprehensive survey which I conducted in order to evaluate the current needs and challenges faced by IT professionals, when it comes to the context of career planning and CV building, the survey garnered more than 200 responses which make the survey and data collecting more successful. This was aimed to gather insights about CV creation challenges, CV updating frequency, confidence in the efficacy of existing CVs, use of online CV builders or templates, openness to considering AI-driven career suggestions, and degree of trust in AI recommendations without human validation.

The survey results are as below.

1. The first question was aimed to understand how often people update their CV to get an idea how often does individuals update their CV

1. How often do you update your CV?

[More Details](#)

Once a month	46
Every 3-6 months	91
Once a Year	43
Rarely	23
Only when job hunting	20

Figure 2 Survey Question 1

2. The second question was to gain insights on what challenges people face when updating and creating their CV.

2. What challenges do you face while updating or creating your CV? (Select all that apply)

[More Details](#)

Tailoring for a specific job role	138
Identifying relevant skills to hig...	124
Formatting and design	96
Understanding current IT indust...	84
Other	1

Figure 3 Survey Question 2

3. This question identifies the current confidence on their CV when landing a job in the IT sector.

3. How confident are you in your current CV's effectiveness in landing you a job in the IT sector?

[More Details](#)

Extremely confident	26
Somewhat confident	50
Neutral	63
Somewhat not confident	70
Extremely not confident	14

Figure 4 Survey Question 3

4. Fourth question identified that more than half of the contestants has used online CV builders or templates in the past.

4. Have you used any online CV builders or templates in the past?

[More Details](#)

Insights

Yes	130
No	93

Figure 5 Survey Question 4

5. This question targets people who said yes to the previous question to see whether they are satisfied or not with it.

5. If yes, was your experience with online CV builders satisfactory?

[More Details](#)

Very satisfied	26
Satisfied	45
Neutral	44
Unsatisfied	21
Very unsatisfied	8

Figure 6 Survey Question 5

6. This question targets to see if the users are willing to use AI driven tools when it comes to based on career path suggestions based on the users skills and experiences.

6. Would you be open to using an AI-driven tool that provides personalized career path suggestions based on your skills and experiences?

[More Details](#)

Insights

Definitely	85
Maybe	83
Unsure	34
Probably Not	13
Definitely not	8

Figure 7 Survey Question 6

7. Then I requested the users to give their opinions on what features they are willing to use with the help of AI.

7. What features would you value most in an AI-driven career guidance tool? (Select up to three)

[More Details](#)

Personalized CV feedback	112
Career path suggestions	144
Mock interview questions for IT ...	97
Recommendations for further tr...	89
Insights on current IT industry tr...	77
Other	0

Figure 8 Survey Question 7

8. This question was to identify how users normally seek advice or insights regarding their career path.

8. How do you currently seek advice or insights about your IT career path? (Select all that apply)

[More Details](#)

Peer discussions	75
Online forums or communities	84
Mentorship or coaching	67
Career counselors or HR profess...	62
Independent research (books, ar...	130
Other	0

Figure 9 Survey Question 8

9. Since Job Mock Interview feature is interesting, I dedicated an entire question to seek the opinion regarding this particular feature.

9. In your opinion, how valuable would real-time AI advice be during a live job interview, suggesting responses or guiding conversations?

[More Details](#)

[Insights](#)

Extremely valuable	61
Somewhat valuable	91
Neutral	50
Somewhat not valuable	15
Extremely not valuable	6

Figure 10 Survey Question 9

10. To get an understanding, I sought individuals' opinions regarding when it comes to the career progression in the IT sector, what are their biggest challenges or concerns so I may be able to come up with a solution to cope with them.

10. In terms of career progression in the IT sector, what's your biggest challenge or concern?

[More Details](#)

Figure 11 Survey Question 10

11. Sometimes when it comes to a platform regarding this, there are few concerns regarding AI integration. Within this question, I was able to get a better understanding of what people are thinking of.

11. If you were to invest in an AI-driven career guidance platform, what would be your top priority?

[More Details](#)

Figure 12 Survey Question 11

12. & 13. The last two questions give an idea how much people trusts using AI.

12. If an AI tool suggested a career path or role outside your current expertise but aligned with your talent skills, would you consider it?

[More Details](#)

● Definitely consider	64
● Might consider	92
● Not Sure	46
● Probably not consider	12
● Definitely not consider	9

Figure 13 Survey Question 12

13. To what extent do you trust AI-driven recommendations without human validation in career planning? (1 Being lowest and 5 being highest)

[More Details](#)

Insights

3.52
Average Rating

Figure 14 Survey Question 13

Frequency of CV Updates

Upon analyzing the data, the survey's findings showed that different IT professionals update their resumes at different frequencies. 40.81%, a sizable percentage, stated they updated their resumes every three to six months. This frequent updating cycle may be a sign of the dynamic nature of the IT industry, where workers should maintain current knowledge and expertise and keep updated themselves. By comparison, 19.28% of respondents update their CV once a year, and 20.63% do so once a month. A lesser percentage, 10.31%, seldom updates their resumes, and 8.97% only do so while applying for jobs. The differences in methods for career management in the IT industry are highlighted by this diversity in update frequency.

Challenges faced during CV Creation

The survey participants identified several significant challenges they faced when writing or revising their resumes. One hundred and thirty-eight respondents found it difficult to customize their resumes for a specific job position, making it the most common problem. According to 124 respondents, the second most significant challenge was selecting relevant skills to highlight. Other noteworthy obstacles were understanding current trends in the IT industry (84 mentions) and formatting and design issues (96 mentions). Interestingly, only one responder mentioned the difficulty of making their CV look professional, indicating that most IT professionals do not consider this a top concern.

Confidence in the CV Effectiveness

The survey results revealed that job seekers in the information technology sector have varying levels of confidence in their resumes. About 31.39% of respondents were slightly unconfident, while 28.25% were neutral, indicating some doubts about their resumes' effectiveness. Only 11.66% of respondents were very confident, and 22.42% felt confident about their CVs. However, 6.28% of respondents expressed an extreme lack of confidence, which may suggest a lack of knowledge of industry standards or an inability to construct a good CV.

Usage of Online Resume Builders & Templates

Most of the survey participants (58.30%) reported using online resume builders and templates, indicating a significant reliance on these digital resources. This trend towards utilizing digital tools to create resumes may stem from their accessible and structured support whereas other respondents reported not using any online CV generation tools.

Consideration of AI-Driven Career Paths

Around 41.26% of respondents stated that they would consider proposals for AI-driven career paths. Among those, 28.70% expressed openness to taking AI recommendations into account and 20.63% remained uncertain, while only a small percentage expressed willingness to embrace career pathways led by AI, either certainly (4.04%) or possibly (5.38%). These findings show the growing interest in career planning powered by AI.

Trust in AI without Human Oversight

When asked about their trust in AI recommendations, 31.84% of respondents reported a high degree of trust (rating 4 out of 5), highlighting a strong sense of confidence in AI's potential. The middle ground

was maintained by 26.01% of respondents (rating 3 out of 5), while 22.42% demonstrated complete trust (rating 5 out of 5). However, the 14.80% who expressed reluctance (rating 2 out of 5) and the 4.93% who exhibited significant skepticism (rating 1 out of 5) suggest that some suspicion remains.

Figure 15 Comprehensive Insights from Survey

Figure 16 Summarized Version of Survey Results

In conclusion, this survey clarifies the diverse approaches and viewpoints held by IT professionals concerning the advancement of their careers and the creation of their resumes.

The insights emphasize the need for tailored, intelligent CV tools and AI-based career advisory services that resonate with the unique needs of the IT workforce.

Qualitative Approach:

The qualitative methodology encompasses a thorough examination of secondary sources, which includes scrutinizing literature reviews, conducting market research, and analyzing academic publications. This systematic approach enables a comprehensive understanding of the current landscape and emerging trends in the IT sector, as well as the various challenges faced within the industry. Such a multifaceted appraisal facilitates the acquisition of nuanced insights and expert perspectives, thereby establishing a strong foundation for the research.

This dual-methodology approach ensures a comprehensive comprehension of the subject matter, combining primary data obtained through targeted surveys with insights gleaned from reputable secondary sources.

Empirical Research Method (ERM)

The project adhered to the principles of ERM and was methodically observed and developed accordingly. The blend of qualitative insights from the literature study and quantitative data from the surveys allowed for a holistic assessment of the project's implications. As a result, I was able to create my artifact as a tangible manifestation of theoretical concepts applied to the practical endeavor of career guidance through AI.

Data Synthesis and Interpretation:

The obtained data was carefully evaluated to uncover patterns and trends that led the platform's iterative development. This strategy made sure that the narrative of the data was effectively translated into relevant insights. This made building the artifact more impactful for society.

Application of the Scientific Approach and Build Methodology:

The project followed the scientific approach in generating a hypothesis, acquiring data through experiments (tests and surveys), and interpreting this data to produce conclusions that drove future cycles of development. Primary data collection was executed via surveys to ensure that there is a comprehensive understanding of the target demographics needs and expectations.

When it comes to the Build Methodology, the project mainly focuses on creating an artifact showing the practical application of AI when it comes to career guidance and aligning with the research outline. The process was well aligned with the initial research outline ensuring the development trajectory remained true to the foundational objectives of the research.

Testing Methodology

When it comes to testing, various strategies were followed. The process involves a multi-layered testing strategy, including both software and hardware examinations to assure robust performance and

compatibility. User testing played a crucial role in offering real-world feedback and insights. I was able to make the product better based on the user feedback. This ensured that we were able to refine and enhance the user experience to ensure the platform's alignment with the user needs. I also did unit testing on the product to verify the integrity and the reliability of the individual components of the platform. This phase was essential in developing the platform's usability and functionality.

These methodologies collectively provided a comprehensive evaluation, aligning the platform's capabilities with the needs and expectations of IT professionals.

Ethical Rigor

Research activities were maintained within strict ethical boundaries throughout the project. Participants' consent, privacy and data are aligned with legal standards and ethical research practices. All the research activities were conducted in a compliant way by obeying the legal standards and following the research practices.

Adhering to these principles, a viable and user-centric solution was successfully produced. In conclusion the application of these methodologies made me to create a solution which is not only technically sound, but also ethically responsible. This approach ensured that the development of the platform addresses the requirements.

Professional, Legal and Ethical issues

While conducting this research, recognizing the gravity of the legal and ethical considerations especially in a field which intersects with technology and the personal data, every step was taken to ensure the adherence to the highest standards of ethical research.

Commitment to Best Practices: The project aligns with the highest professional standards, ensuring the tool's functionality and reliability align with user expectations and industry demands.

GDPR Compliance and Data Privacy: Strict adherence to legal standards, particularly GDPR, underlines the project's commitment to data security and user privacy. No user data is permanently stored in the backend. This ensured that this project did not infringe upon any legal boundaries and held the rights of the participants.

Ethical Integrity in AI Utilization: The project's ethical framework ensures AI recommendations are fair, unbiased, and respect user autonomy, addressing potential ethical concerns in AI implementation. Survey participants were provided with clear information about the purpose of this research.

Data Collection: Also the data collected through the survey is completely anonymous and is accessible only by me. I have also mentioned in the survey form that this is for research purposes. This involved obtaining informed consent from all participants involved in the survey and the user testing phases. This ensures the voluntary participation was there to maintain the ethical rigor. No data was used beyond the scope of this research and all the data will be disposed appropriately upon the completion of the project.

The present research endeavor was executed with unwavering commitment to upholding ethical standards, adhering to legal compliance and professional integrity. This approach ensured not only the protection and respect to the participants, but also contributed to the credibility of the research findings, thereby strengthening the scholarship of the study.

Project Progress/Project Management

This section covers the execution of this project with a focus on methods. In my research on project management, I have emphasized the use of adaptive planning and Agile methodologies to promote project flexibility and incremental delivery. Throughout the journey of the research and bringing the AI Driven CV generator and career recommendation system to life, we have tracked every single step to ensure that we are on a good track.

Navigating with JIRA: The roadmap of this project was delineated within JIRA, which is widely regarded as one of the best project management tools. This is where we meticulously disassembled the project into more manageable components. Each individual component of the Work Breakdown Structure (WBS) acted as a distinctive fragment, seamlessly fitting into the larger framework of our overarching objective. JIRA functioned as our navigational compass, guiding us through moments of potential overwhelm in relation to the project's scope, while also aiding us in adapting to unexpected obstacles. The comprehensive breakdown of the WBS can be found below.

Figure 17 JIRA Timeline

Tracking Time: This project was initiated by targeting 400hrs and we didn't waste any time. By tracking how long we spent on each task, we learned a lot about where our efforts were best spent and to do the work efficiently. Time management tools were essential, in an environment like this where project scopes are subject to change. By using time-boxing for tasks and prioritizing features I was able to ensure that crucial components were developed and tested before the project deadline.

I have used TrackingTime, Time Tracker software to track the time efficiently. (trackingtime, n.d.)

Figure 18 Time Tracker Dashboard Overview

We have broken down into 10 main tasks where, the time tracker sheet was recorded accordingly.

TASKS	USERS	WORKED/ESTIMATED HR
Testing		18 hr
Research & Development		32:10 hr
Project Proposal		13:50 hr
Literature Review		13:30 hr
Learning/Improving Skill		5 hr
Frontend Coding		143:39 hr
Documentation		47:40 hr
Develop ML Model		77:14 hr
Collecting Surveys		33:09 hr
Backend Coding		30:30 hr

Figure 19 Effort Hour Summary

Git for Collaboration: I have used Git to store the code history. We've included a sample snapshot of the commit history of the Machine Learning code.

Figure 20 Git Commit Chart

Learning from Feedback: When we shared our prototype with friends and colleagues, their insights were valuable. We listened, took notes, and went back and improved most of them.

Adhering to Standards: We've kept a close eye on industry standards and guidelines, ensuring that what we build not only functions in theory but also meet the real-world expectations and ethical considerations associated with AI technology.

Throughout the course of the development process, I actively sought feedback on a regular basis, following a sprint-based approach whereby input was collected and seamlessly integrated into the development cycle which enabled me to effectively evaluate the project's progress at various stages of its evolution. The project benefitted greatly from this continuous feedback loop, maintaining its integrity and effectiveness.

Throughout the duration of the project, obstacles and challenges were recorded and thoroughly investigated, where I transformed the roadblocks into chances where I was able to increase my knowledge and develop new skills which benefited my personal growth.

Design and Implementation

The design and implementation phase of this project represented a crucible of creativity and problem-solving, where theoretical planning met practical execution. This phase was meticulously documented to capture the iterative process of developing the AI-driven CV generator and career recommendation system.

Diagrams

Below are the UML (Unified Modeling Language) diagrams related to the project. Job Seeker can also be considered as the User.

Use Case Diagram

The Use Case Diagram presented here illustrates the interactions between users and the ResumeAI360 system, which is designed to facilitate various core functionalities, including CV generation, IT career prediction, mock interviews, and AI-powered career advice. The diagram depicts the systematic processing of users' inputs and preferences through the use of machine learning (ML) models and the OpenAI API, resulting in personalized and tailored outcomes such as a generated CV, career predictions, interview questions, and professional guidance.

Figure 21 Use Case Diagram

Entity Relationship Diagram (ERD)

The ERD for the ResumeAI360 system maps out the data structure of the system, highlighting the connections between various entities. These entities include User, CV, Mock Interview Question, Career Suggestion and Career Prediction, each defined by their unique attributes. The ERD serves as a visual representation of how these entities interact with each other, offering a comprehensive overview of the data flow within the system.

Figure 22 ER Diagram

System Architecture

This diagram shows the users interaction with our platform. The user interfaces with the platform through a frontend hosted on Vercel. From there, the user can access three services: CV Generation Service, ML Model Service (hosted on Render), and Mock Interview Service and Career Advice (powered by OpenAI).

Figure 23 System Architecture Diagram

Data Flow Diagram (DFD)
Generate CV DFD

Figure 24 Generate CV DFD

Predict IT career with ML Model DFD

Figure 25 Predict IT career with ML Model DFD

Mock Interview DFD

Figure 26 Mock Interview DFD

AI Suggestions DFD

Figure 27 AI Suggestions DFD

Technology Stack

The development of this platform can be divided into two main components as frontend and backend.

Front End : The user interface was created by using HTML, CSS and JavaScript. These technologies were chosen due to its flexibility and robustness when it comes to creating response and interactive web applications. HTML was the foundation; CSS was used for the layout and the styling and JavaScript is used for interactivity and dynamic content manipulation.

Back End : We have used Python for the back-end development. It served as the backbone for processing user requests, interfacing with the machine learning model as well as generating results.

Hosting and Deployment: The front-end component was hosted on Vercel, known for its ease of use and efficiency in deploying static sites. The back-end was hosted on Render, chosen for its scalability and support for containerized applications. This separation of front-end and back-end hosting provided both flexibility and robust performance.

System Integration

The integration between the front end and back end was achieved through API calls. An example of this integration is evident in the code snippet provided, where a POST request is sent from the front end to the back-end service hosted on Render. This setup ensured seamless communication between the user interface and the server, facilitating real-time data processing and response.

```
const handleSubmit = async () => {
  try{
    setDialogOpen(true);
    setDataAi(null);
    const response = await fetch('https://resumeai360-backend.onrender.com/suggest', {
      method: 'POST',
      headers: {
        'Content-Type': 'application/json',
      },
      body: JSON.stringify({ user_career: career}),
    });
  }
```

Figure 28 System Integration Code

Dataset

A very important part when it comes to building the career recommendation machine learning model was to choose an appropriate dataset to train the model. After testing multiple datasets, the "IT Career Proficiency Dataset," initially published in 2022 by Arun Jain and available on Mendeley Data and Kaggle, was chosen. This dataset can be accessed via the following Medeley Data Link ([Mendeley Link](#)) (Jain, 2022), with its DOI being ([DOI Link](#)) and metadata accessible at ([MetaData Link](#))

The dataset has an approximately 9000 survey responses detailing proficiency in various IT skills making it highly relevant to my projects focus and scope.

The decision to select this dataset was based on several key factors.

- **Alignment with Project Requirements:** This dataset directly aligns with the objectives of this project. Upon going through I noticed that the content would be easier and directly support the models ability to make informed suggestions based on the skill proficiency
- **Data Quality :** After evaluating, it was found out that this dataset was well-structured, almost clean, and required minimal preprocessing. This reduced the time and resources needed for data cleaning and preprocessing allowing to save time more to focus on the model development and training.
- **Well Balanced Data :** This dataset is a well balanced dataset which can provide unbiased suggestions
- **Relevance and Recency :** Published in 2022, this dataset is both relevant and current showcasing latest skills and trends in rapidly evolving IT industry.
- **Comparative Analysis with Other Dataset :** Other datasets either lacked the depth of information which I was seeking for this project or were not as closely aligned with the projects requirements.

Selection of this dataset was a good decision which significantly contributed to the effectiveness of the machine learning model. Due to its relevance, quality and the alignment with the project goals, this helped to build and train the Machine learning model which is capable to provide accurate and personalized career advice to individuals in IT Sector.

Machine Learning Model

After checking out various models, the RandomForestClassifier was selected due to its high accuracy and robustness. The model was built and tested using Jupyter Notebook. The RandomForest model was trained to analyze user inputs and suggest appropriate career paths.

Testing & Developing the Machine Learning Model

To develop a robust predictive model for suggesting suitable career, I decided to compare RandomForestClassifier, LogisticRegression, SVC, KNeighborsClassifier, and GradientBoostingClassifier which were evaluated based on their mean cross-validation (CV) score to ensure a fair and unbiased assessment of their performance.

Figure 29 ML Model Performance Comparison

The RandomForestClassifier emerged as the selected model for the final deployment due to its performance which was the highest compared with the other many models. This model showed a high level of generalization when subjected to unseen data which demonstrated a high CV score.

Key Reasons for Selecting RandomForestClassifier

- In terms of accuracy, RandomForestClassifier provided reliable predictions which is an important factor for the project
- This model showed a high level of generalization when subjected to unseen data
- Unlike some other models, this model is able to process both categorical as well as numerical data
- With the ensemble approach, I was able to combine predictions from multiple decision trees

The below snippet includes the initialization of the ensemble models, cross-validation, training, and evaluation on the test set. Additionally, it includes the extraction and visualization of feature importance from the RandomForestClassifier.

```

# Initialize models
models = {
    'RandomForestClassifier': RandomForestClassifier(n_estimators=100, random_state=42),
    'GradientBoostingClassifier': GradientBoostingClassifier(random_state=42)
}

# Train and evaluate models using cross-validation
model_performance = {}
for name, model in models.items():
    model_pipeline = Pipeline(['model', model])
    cv_score = cross_val_score(model_pipeline, X_train, y_train, cv=cv)
    model_performance[name] = cv_score.mean()
    print(f"{name} CV score: {cv_score.mean():.2f} (+/- {cv_score.std():.2f})")

# Train and evaluate models on test set
for name, model in models.items():
    model.fit(X_train, y_train)
    predictions = model.predict(X_test)
    accuracy = accuracy_score(y_test, predictions)
    print(f"{name} accuracy: {accuracy:.2f}")
    print(classification_report(y_test, predictions))

# Feature importance from RandomForest
rf_model = RandomForestClassifier(n_estimators=100, random_state=42)
rf_model.fit(X_train, y_train)
importances = rf_model.feature_importances_
feature_importances = pd.Series(importances, index=X.columns).sort_values(ascending=False)

plt.figure(figsize=(12, 6))
feature_importances.plot(kind='bar')
plt.title("Feature Importance from Random Forest")
plt.show()

```

Figure 30 Train Evaluate Model Code Snippet

Confusion Matrix

The predictive accuracy was evaluated using a confusion matrix.

Figure 31 Confusion Matrix

It's impressive to see how accurately the classifier matches the predicted labels with the true labels, as indicated by the diagonal elements of the matrix. It's evident that the classifier successfully determines the appropriate career paths based on the given skill set. This level of accuracy is a good sign. The indicator of the classifier's potential in suggesting career paths in a reliable guidance system is clearly shown in this image.

Moreover, when it comes to the non-diagonal elements of the matrix which represents the misclassifications, and the absence of non-zero values in these positions demonstrates the model's ability to classify with high precision without any confusion between different labels. The classifier's

capability to distinguish between different skill sets is remarkable, which showcases the testament to the model's strong performance.

Overall, the high level of accuracy achieved by the classifier is encouraging and highlights its potential in guiding individuals towards suitable career paths. This is a significant step forward in the development of a reliable career guidance system.

Data Preparation & Management

Data Preparation

Data Cleaning : This was the initial step. This included things such as handling missing values, correcting various inconsistencies and filtering out irrelevant information. The main purpose of this stage is to refine the dataset where it could be used to train the machine learning model effectively.

```
● ● ●  
  
# Checking for missing values  
  
missing_values = data.isnull().sum()  
print(missing_values)
```

Figure 32 Data Cleaning Snippet

Data Analysis : After cleaning the dataset, we did data analysis which covered various activities such as identifying various patterns, anomalies and correlations which could impact the models training and the performance. Upon doing the data analysis we were able to gain a deeper understanding of the nature and the structure of the dataset.

Data Visualization: Inorder to clearly understand the findings from the data analysis we employed few data visualization techniques using tools like Matplotlib and Seaborn in Python which was used to create graphical representation of the data.

```
● ● ●  
  
# Confusion Matrix  
from sklearn.metrics import confusion_matrix  
import seaborn as sns  
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt  
  
y_pred = best_model.predict(X_test)  
cm = confusion_matrix(y_test, y_pred)  
  
# Plot the confusion matrix as a heatmap  
plt.figure(figsize=(10, 8))  
sns.heatmap(cm, annot=True, fmt="d", cmap="Blues", cbar=False,  
            xticklabels=role_encoder.classes_, yticklabels=role_encoder.classes_)  
plt.title('Confusion Matrix')  
plt.xlabel('Predicted Label')  
plt.ylabel('True Label')  
plt.show()
```

Figure 33 Confusion Matrix Code Snippet

```
# Visualizing Distribution of Roles
plt.figure(figsize=(20, 10))
ax = sns.countplot(data=data, x='Role', palette='viridis')
plt.title('Distribution of Roles', fontsize=20)
plt.xticks(rotation=45, ha='right', fontsize=12)
plt.yticks(fontsize=12)
plt.xlabel('Role', fontsize=15)
plt.ylabel('Count', fontsize=15)

# Add count annotations on top of each bar
for p in ax.patches:
    ax.annotate(f'{{int(p.get_height())}}', (p.get_x() + p.get_width() / 2.,
    p.get_height()),
                ha='center', va='bottom', fontsize=12, color='black')

plt.tight_layout()
plt.show()
```

Figure 34 Visualize Distribution of Roles Snippet

Data Management

When it comes to this project, it is important to focus on ethical handling of user data. In line with this, no personal data is stored in the system. This was done to ensure the security and privacy of user data while still being compliant with data protection regulations and standards.

Challenges and Solutions

The journey wasn't without its hiccups. Early on, we encountered a challenge when it came to the dataset which we found. When it came to the data pre-processing, the model wasn't confident when it came to the training and split data part. Also there were few formats which didn't support where we turned those categorical values into numerical values to tackle this. By refining our parsing algorithms and including additional data sanitization steps, we resolved these discrepancies.

Also there were few areas which we lacked the knowledge of where we had to tackle them down after doing some learning and development.

The development process encountered some challenges, one of which was ensuring the responsiveness of the front end across different devices and browsers. To address this issue, responsive design principles were employed, and testing was conducted on multiple platforms. Another challenge was in fine-tuning the machine learning model to cater to the diverse needs of IT professionals. This challenge was overcome by iteratively adjusting the model parameters and training it on a varied dataset.

Other

Testing and Validation : The platform went through various testing stages to ensure that frontend and the backend works harmoniously.

Design Philosophy: When it comes to the design phase, we followed a user-centric philosophy. We endeavored to create a system that not only functioned with technical precision but also with an intuitive understanding of the user's experience. This meant designing an interface that was not just pleasing but also very simple and responsive.

Results

This section presents the detailing outcomes achieved throughout my project where I have developed a CV Generator tool as well as a career recommendation system for IT professionals using AI.

Artifact Development

When developing the artifact, I was able to successfully integrate advance machine learning model along with a user friendly interface.

Functionality and Performance

Career Recommendation Accuracy

The platform's core functionality which is to provide career recommendations based on the users inputs was tested extensively. The results indicated a high level of accuracy. This was a significant achievement confirming the effectiveness of the model.

CV Generation

The CV Generation feature functioned seamlessly offers users multiple templates and customization options

AI Suggestions

AI Suggestions gives things such as Career advice, required skill sets and recommended qualifications.

Interview

This feature will offer a mock interview questionnaire based on the role provided by the user. It will ask relevant questions regarding the role and based on the users typed answer, it will provide feedback based on it.

Main Code Snippets

Connecting Backend to Front End

In this part, we will be speaking about how I established a connection between the backend and frontend components, ensuring seamless communication and data exchange. The process involves the following steps:

1. **Fetch API Request:** Fetch API in frontend JavaScript code to send an asynchronous HTTP POST request to the backend endpoint (<https://resumeai360-backend.onrender.com/predict>).
2. **Request Configuration:** The request is configured with appropriate headers, specifying the content type as 'application/json'. This ensures that the backend correctly interprets the received data as JSON format.
3. **Error Handling:** Error handling is implemented to catch any issues during the request process. If the response from the backend is not successful an error is thrown, displaying the HTTP status

code. This ensures that any communication or processing errors are effectively caught and can be addressed promptly.

```
try {
    const response = await fetch('https://resumeai360-backend.onrender.com/predict', {
      method: 'POST',
      headers: {
        'Content-Type': 'application/json',
      },
      body: JSON.stringify(ratings),
    });

    if (!response.ok) {
      throw new Error(`HTTP error! Status: ${response.status}`);
    }
  }
```

Figure 35 Connect Backend to Frontend Snippet

Implementing the Model in Backend

In our research, we integrated a predictive model into our backend API, enhancing the Career prediction functionality. The key components of this integration are as follows:

1. **Model Loading:** Loaded a pre-trained model and a role encoder using Python's **pickle** module. The **model.pkl** and **role_encoder.pkl** files store the trained machine learning model and label encoder, respectively.
2. **Prediction Endpoint:** The **/predict** endpoint is set up to handle POST requests which retrieves the input data in JSON format, which contains the features necessary for making a prediction.
3. **Data Processing and Prediction:** The features from the request data are converted into a NumPy array and reshaped appropriately for compatibility with the model. The model then computes the probabilities of various classes for the given input.
4. **Top Three Predictions:** We extract the indices of the top three class probabilities using **np.argsort** and reverse the order to get the highest probabilities first. These indices are then transformed back into their corresponding role labels using the **role_encoder**.
5. **Response Formation:** The endpoint returns a JSON response containing the top three predicted roles, providing users with insightful career recommendations based on their input features.

```
● ● ●

# Load the model and the label encoder
model = pickle.load(open('model.pkl', 'rb'))
role_encoder = pickle.load(open('role_encoder.pkl', 'rb'))

@app.route('/predict', methods=['POST'])
def predict():
    data = request.get_json()
    features = np.array([data[feature] for feature in data.keys()]).reshape(1,
-1)

    class_probs = model.predict_proba(features)

    top_three_indices = np.argsort(class_probs[0])[::-1][:3]

    top_three_roles = role_encoder.inverse_transform(top_three_indices)

    return jsonify({'predictions': top_three_roles.tolist()})
```

Figure 36 Implementing the Model to Backend Snippet

Implementing Open AI

In this research, I integrated the OpenAI API to enhance our Mock Interview platform and AI Advice feature. The implementation involves the following key components:

1. **Environment Setup:** I began by importing necessary modules, including **openai** from the OpenAI Python library and **load_dotenv** for environment variable management which allowed me to securely access the OpenAI API key stored in an env file.
2. **API Key Configuration:** Utilizing **load_dotenv()**, the load environment variables and set the OpenAI API key. This key is retrieved using **os.getenv("OPEN_AI_API_KEY")** and assigned to **openai.api_key**, establishing a secure connection to the OpenAI services.
3. **Completion Function:** The **get_completion** function is designed to interact with the OpenAI API. It takes a user prompt and an optional model specification (defaulting to "gpt-3.5-turbo"). The response from the API is then returned.
4. **Data Reduction Function:** The **get_reduced_data** function serves as a streamlined interface for obtaining concise data. It receives a prompt, passes it to the **get_completion** function, and returns the completion directly.

Through this implementation, I successfully leveraged the advanced capabilities of GPT models from OpenAI, significantly enriching the user experience on our platform by providing smart, context-aware content.

```

import os
from dotenv import load_dotenv
import openai

load_dotenv()

openai.api_key = os.getenv("OPEN_AI_API_KEY")

def get_completion(prompt, model="gpt-3.5-turbo"):
    messages = [{"role": "user", "content": prompt}]

    response = openai.ChatCompletion.create(
        model=model,
        messages=messages,
        temperature=0.2, # less random and more concise
    )

    return response.choices[0].message["content"]

def get_reduced_data(prompt, model="gpt-3.5-turbo", max_points=5):
    completion = get_completion(prompt, model)
    # points = completion.split('\n')[:max_points]
    # return ' '.join(points)
    return completion

```

Figure 37 Open AI implementation Snippet

Integrate Career Advice, Career Skills and Career Qualifications in Backend

In our research, we extended the functionality of our backend API to include career advice, essential skills, and qualification recommendations. This feature is encapsulated in the **/suggest** endpoint.

1. **Data Retrieval:** Upon receiving a POST request, the API extracts the 'user_career' field from the JSON data. If this field is absent, an error response is generated.
2. **Content Generation:** For each user-specified career, the API constructs three separate prompts: one for certifications or qualifications, another for essential skills, and the last for general career advice. These prompts are processed through the **get_reduced_data** function, which interacts with the OpenAI API to generate relevant content.
3. **Response Composition:** The API aggregates the generated recommendations for certifications, skills, and career advice into a single JSON response.
4. **Error Handling:** The endpoint includes robust error handling, both for potential issues in data processing and unforeseen exceptions, ensuring a reliable user experience.

This enhancement to the backend API not only broadens the scope of our platform but also provides users with valuable insights into career progression, skill development, and professional qualifications.

```

@app.route('/suggest', methods=['POST'])
def get_recommendations():
    try:
        data = request.json

        if 'user_career' not in data:
            return jsonify({'error': 'Missing "user_career" in request data'}), 400

        user_career = data['user_career']

        certifications_prompt = f"I am a {user_career}. Can you suggest which certifications or qualifications are
needed for this career?"
        skills_prompt = f"I am a {user_career}. Can you suggest which skills are essential for this career?"
        advice_prompt = f"I am a {user_career}. Do you have any general career advice for someone in this field?"

        try:
            certifications = get_reduced_data(certifications_prompt)
            skills = get_reduced_data(skills_prompt)
            career_advice = get_reduced_data(advice_prompt)
        except Exception as e:
            return jsonify({'error': f'Error processing data: {str(e)}'}), 500

        response_data = {
            'certifications': certifications,
            'skills': skills,
            'career_advice': career_advice,
        }

        return jsonify(response_data)

    except Exception as e:
        return jsonify({'error': f'Unexpected error: {str(e)}'}), 500

```

Figure 38 Integrate Career Advice, Career Skills and Career Qualifications in Backend Snippet

Integrate Mock Interview API in Backend

To enable a mock interview feature, I developed a unique backend API. `/interview` and `/feedback` are the two main endpoints of this API. The `/feedback` endpoint offers helpful criticism on the user's responses, while the `/interview` endpoint creates personalized interview questions based on the user's chosen career path. The `get_reduced_data` function is used by both endpoints to generate content, and error handling mechanisms are included. This method provides individualized interview training and exemplifies the use of dynamic content creation in educational technology.

```

@app.route('/interview', methods=['POST'])
def get_questions():
    try:
        data = request.json

        if 'user_career' not in data:
            return jsonify({'error': 'Missing "user_career" in request data'}), 400

        user_career = data['user_career']

        interview_prompt = f"I am preparing for an interview for {user_career}. Can you ask me five interview
questions related to this? no intro no conclusion just 5 lines of questions"
        questions = get_reduced_data(interview_prompt)

        response_data = {
            'questions': questions
        }
        return jsonify(response_data)

    except Exception as e:
        return jsonify({'error': f'Unexpected error: {str(e)}'}), 500

@app.route('/feedback', methods=['POST'])
def get_feedback():
    try:
        data = request.json

        question = data['question']
        answer = data['answer']

        feedback_prompt = f"Given the question: '{question}', the user provided the following answer: '{answer}'. Can
you provide constructive feedback on the answer? Highlight strengths and suggest improvements."
        feedback = get_reduced_data(feedback_prompt)

        response_data = {
            'feedback': feedback
        }
        return jsonify(response_data)

    except Exception as e:
        return jsonify({'error': f'Unexpected error: {str(e)}'}), 500

```

Figure 39 Integrate Mock Interview API in Backend Snippet

Backend Hosting

For Backend Hosting, I have used Render. Currently it runs on Python 3 and runs on Singapore Region.

The screenshot shows the Render dashboard interface. At the top, there is a navigation bar with the Render logo and links for Dashboard, Blueprints, Env Groups, Docs, Community, and Help. A 'New +' button and a user profile icon for 'Ahamed' are also visible. Below the navigation bar, the 'Overview' section contains a search bar for services. On the right side of the overview, there are summary statistics: 'Active 1', 'Suspended 0', and 'All 1'. The main part of the dashboard is a table with the following columns: SERVICE NAME, STATUS, TYPE, RUNTIME, REGION, and LAST DEPLOYED. The table contains one entry: 'ResumeAI360-Backend' with a status of 'Deployed', type of 'Web Service', runtime of 'Python 3', region of 'Singapore', and last deployed '7 hours ago'.

SERVICE NAME	STATUS	TYPE	RUNTIME	REGION	LAST DEPLOYED
ResumeAI360-Backend	Deployed	Web Service	Python 3	Singapore	7 hours ago

Figure 40 Backend Hosting Overview

Storing the Open AI API Key

I have stored the Open AI API key in the environment section in Render. This eliminates the need of including and exposing the API key in my repository.

Figure 41 Storing the Open AI API Key

Frontend Hosting

The main web app is hosted on vercel server. I will be using the free version for this. I have connected my Github repository for this.

Figure 42 Frontend Hosting

Production Deployment

Build Logs

Runtime Logs

Instant Rollback

The deployment that is available to your visitors.

Deployment
resume-ai-360-n4sdyhuul-ahamed-careems-projects.vercel.app

Domains
resume-ai-360.vercel.app +2

Status Created
● Ready 7h ago by amcareem

Source
main
-o- be2f522 Merge pull request #4 from amcareem/interview interview function impl...

Figure 43 Frontend Hosting Status

Screenshots and Visual Evidence

To provide a clearer understanding of the platform's functionality and design, I have included screenshots of the system in operation. These images, found in the appendices, showcase the interface, the career suggestion process, and examples of the CV templates.

CV Template Generation

This is the homepage of the artifact. There are 4 templates where the user can choose from.

Figure 44 Homepage

Upon Selecting one, the user will have to fill the required details to generate a template.

The screenshot shows the 'CV Input' form. On the left is a sidebar menu with four options: 'Personal Info' (selected), 'Work Experience', 'Education', and 'Key Skills'. The main form area contains a 'Change Profile Photo' button and a series of input fields for personal information: First Name, Last Name, Email, Mobile, Address, City, State, Postal Code, Github, Twitter, Youtube, Stack Overflow, Quora, Website, and Objective. A 'Next' button is located at the bottom right of the form.

Figure 45 CV Input

Based on the filled information, a CV will be generated where the user can save it as a pdf to his/her device. Below is a sample CV.

First Name Last Name
Job Title 1

20 Address 9876543210
Road

Email : EmailEmailEmail @gmail .com

GithubGithubGithubGithub .com

Stack OverflowStack Overflow .com

www .WebsiteWebsite .com

Professional Experience

- Job Title 1 Organization Name (2022 - Present)

Education

School

(2010 - 2020)
Diploma Name (Subject)
Institute (2017)

University University

Degree Degree in Domain
(2022 - 2026)
certificate Name
Organization (2022 - 2025)

Key Skills

- Key Skills
- Key Skills 2

Languages

- Languages - Proficiency : Intermediate

Figure 46 Sample Generated CV

Career Prediction

Below is the IT career prediction page where the users can include their current skill levels in the below fields. Based on them the model will predict the top 3 recommended career paths.

The screenshot shows a web browser window with the URL `https://resume-ai-360.vercel.app/predict`. The page title is "Career Pathfinder: Uncover Your Best Fit". Below the title, there is a brief description of the tool and a motivational message: "Say goodbye to uncertainty and hello to a clearer vision of your future success!". The main part of the form consists of 17 vertical dropdown menus, each with a skill name: Database Fundamentals, Computer Architecture, Distributed Computing Systems, Cyber Security, Networking, Software Development, Programming Skills, Project Management, Computer Forensics Fundamentals, Technical Communication, AI ML, Software Engineering, Business Analysis, Communication skills, Data Science, Troubleshooting skills, and Graphics Designing. At the bottom of the form is a blue button labeled "GENERATE".

Figure 47 Career Prediction Form

User will have a drop down menu to choose the relevant skills

The screenshot shows a dropdown menu with the following options: Software Engineering, Business Analysis, Average, Communication skills, Poor, Beginner, Average, Intermediate, Professional, Excellent, and Not Interested. The "Average" option is currently selected.

Figure 48 Drop Down Menu Options

After entering the required skills and clicking generate, the model will start to run and predict.

The screenshot shows a vertical list of skills with dropdown menus for each. The skills and their selected values are: Database Fundamentals (Average), Computer Architecture, Distributed Computing Systems, Cyber Security (Excellent), Networking (Intermediate), Software Development, Programming Skills (Poor), Project Management, Computer Forensics Fundamentals (Excellent), Technical Communication, AI ML, Software Engineering, Business Analysis (Average), Communication skills (Average), Data Science, Troubleshooting skills (Professional), and Graphics Designing. A blue 'GENERATE' button is at the bottom. A white modal box in the center is titled 'Predicting Careers' and contains a blue hourglass icon.

Figure 49 Sample Input for Prediction

After that, It will display the top 3 suitable career roles

Figure 50 Sample Output

Mock Interview

Below is the page for the mock interview. After entering the role, it will display the relevant questions.

The screenshot shows a web browser at the URL <https://resume-ai-360.vercel.app/interview>. The navigation menu includes: AI Suggestions, Predict Career, Resume Templates, My Resumes, Interview (highlighted), and About Us. The main content area features the heading "Interview Mastery: Elevate Your Success" and a subheading "Explore our interview preparation tool that provides immediate feedback on your responses, helping you refine your skills and boost your chances of success. With just a few clicks, gain valuable insights to enhance your performance and confidently navigate the interview landscape." Below this is a blue link: "Bid farewell to uncertainty and embrace a clearer path to your future triumphs!". A form with the placeholder text "Enter your Career Choice" and a "LET'S START THE INTERVIEW" button is centered on the page.

Figure 51 Mock Interview Interface

After entering the role, relevant questions will be generated and based on the answer for the question it will give its feedback and then we can proceed the next question.

The screenshot shows the same web browser at the URL <https://resume-ai-360.vercel.app/interview>. The navigation menu is the same. The main content area features the heading "INTERVIEW FOR : HELPDESK COORDINATOR" and the subheading "Question 1". Below this is a question: "1. How do you prioritize and manage multiple helpdesk tickets simultaneously to ensure timely resolution and customer satisfaction?". A blue link "Feedback provided by AI" is centered below the question. A scrollable box contains the following feedback:

Strengths:

- The answer acknowledges the importance of following the SLA (Service Level Agreement) in prioritizing and managing multiple helpdesk tickets.
- It implies that the user understands the significance of meeting customer expectations and ensuring timely resolution.

Improvements:

- The answer is quite brief and lacks specific details. It would be beneficial to provide more information on how the SLA is utilized to prioritize and manage tickets.
- Consider expanding on the specific criteria used to prioritize tickets, such as severity levels, impact on business operations, or customer urgency.
- Provide examples of techniques or strategies used to manage multiple tickets simultaneously, such as utilizing a ticketing system.

At the bottom of the scrollable box are two buttons: "WANNA TRY AGAIN" (blue) and "NEXT" (green).

Figure 52 Mock Interview Question Feedback

AI Suggestion

When it comes to the AI suggestion, the user needs to enter a specific job role which he/she desires.

Figure 53 AI Suggestion Input Advice

Then based on the job role, it will display the relevant career advice, skills which needed to be possessed and the qualifications/certifications one should have.

Figure 54 AI Suggestion Output

In conclusion, the results of this artifact demonstrate the successful melding of theoretical research with practical application. The development of this project which included CV generator, a career recommendation system for IT industry along with other AI features were executed with a focus on technological innovation and user experience. The project not only achieved its initial objectives but also provided a foundation for further exploration and development in the field of AI-driven career guidance.

Conclusion

This research project encompasses the development of a CV Generator and an AI driven career recommendation system for IT sector along with other extra AI features/functions.

With the help of the quantitative and qualitative research I was able to create an artifact aligning with the title “CRAFTING THE FUTURE: A STUDY ON THE IMPACT OF INTELLIGENT CV TOOLS AND ASSESSING THE ROLE OF AI IN IT CAREER PATH AND PROFESSIONAL ADVISING” not only a well built product which exceeds the expectations, but also following standards, ethics and best practices of handling users data.

Evaluation of the process and Methodology

The project follows a broad research methodology which includes both quantitative and qualitative approaches. The former entails a meticulously conducted survey that ensures a diverse and representative sample. The latter involves an extensive review of existing literature and market research, providing a solid foundation for the project's direction.

Project management played a main role when it comes to research process with a main focus on agile methodology. The challenges encountered during the research process, particularly in data pre-processing and system integration, were addressed through methodical problem-solving and continual learning.

Evaluation of the Products

The principal artifact excelled in its main functionalities providing accurate career recommendations based on my model, generate career advice, career skills and required certifications for job roles and also have a tool to create beautiful CVs with multiple templates.

Through feedback and insights gathered from a few users regarding the artifact. This process led to improvements, confirming the platform's practicality and user-satisfaction. This approach ensures the relevance of the platform to real-world needs but also demonstrates its effectiveness in meeting user expectations.

Recommendations for Further Work and Discussion

Reflecting on this project there are few paths for future work and improvements.

- **Expanding the Feature Set** : Currently the career prediction is only limited to the IT field sector. By combining multiple datasets, we can increase the career field.
- **UI Enhancements** : Constant improvement of the UI/UX based on evolving user feedback can further improve accessibility and engagement.
- **Scalability and Performance Optimization**: Moving forward, as user base and data volume grow, enhancing the systems scalability and performance will be important.
- **Add More Templates** : It would be better if we can add more CV template options which will give user more options to choose.

In conclusion, this project not only achieved its objectives but also opened pathways for future exploration and development in AI-driven career guidance. Highlighted recommendations offer a roadmap for extending the project impact and scope, ensuring its continued relevance and utility in the dynamic field.

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Appendix

Time Sheet

Below is the overview of the time spent

Solent University - Dissertation Project Timesheet - Ahamed Careem FROM 01/01/2016 TO 01/22/2024

USER	DURATION
Ahamed Careem	414:45
TASK	DURATION
Backend Coding	30:30
Collecting Surveys	33:10
Develop ML Model	77:15
Documentation	47:40
Frontend Coding	143:40
Learning/Improving Skill	5:00
Literature Review	13:30
Project Proposal	13:50
Research & Development	32:10
Testing	18:00

BILLED / WORK TIME
0:00 / 414:45

Solent University - Dissertation Project Timesheet - Ahamed Careem
 FROM 01/01/2016 TO 01/22/2024

USER	DURATION
Ahamed Careem	414:45

TASK	DURATION
Backend Coding	30:30

User	Project	Task	Client	Notes	Date	Billed	Duration	From
Ahamed Careem	Final Dissertation	Backend Coding		Testing model, exporting model and adding to Backend	12/02/2023	X	7:00	6:00 am
Ahamed Careem	Final Dissertation	Backend Coding		Back End Coding	12/04/2023	X	1:00	9:30 pm
Ahamed Careem	Final Dissertation	Backend Coding		Back End Coding	12/05/2023	X	1:00	9:30 pm
Ahamed Careem	Final Dissertation	Backend Coding		Back End Coding	12/06/2023	X	1:00	9:30 pm
Ahamed Careem	Final Dissertation	Backend Coding		Back End Coding	12/07/2023	X	1:00	9:30 pm
Ahamed Careem	Final Dissertation	Backend Coding		Back End Coding	12/08/2023	X	1:00	9:30 pm
Ahamed Careem	Final Dissertation	Backend Coding		Back End Coding	12/09/2023	X	1:00	9:30 pm
Ahamed Careem	Final Dissertation	Backend Coding		Back End Coding	12/10/2023	X	1:00	9:30 pm
Ahamed Careem	Final Dissertation	Backend Coding		Back End Coding	12/11/2023	X	1:00	9:30 pm
Ahamed Careem	Final Dissertation	Backend Coding		Back End Coding	12/12/2023	X	1:00	9:30 pm
Ahamed Careem	Final Dissertation	Backend Coding		Back End Coding	12/13/2023	X	1:00	9:30 pm
Ahamed Careem	Final Dissertation	Backend Coding		Back End Coding	12/14/2023	X	1:00	9:30 pm
Ahamed Careem	Final Dissertation	Backend Coding		Back End Coding	12/15/2023	X	1:00	9:30 pm
Ahamed Careem	Final Dissertation	Backend Coding		Back End Coding	12/16/2023	X	1:00	9:30 pm
Ahamed Careem	Final Dissertation	Backend Coding		Back End Coding	12/17/2023	X	1:00	9:30 pm
Ahamed Careem	Final Dissertation	Backend Coding		Integrate Career Advice, Qualification and Skills using AI	12/30/2023	X	8:00	6:00 am
Ahamed Careem	Final Dissertation	Backend Coding		Final Tweaks	01/17/2024	X	1:30	5:00 am

TASK	DURATION
Collecting Surveys	33:10

User	Project	Task	Client	Notes	Date	Billed	Duration	From
Ahamed Careem	Final Dissertation	Collecting Surveys		Drafting Survey Questions	10/13/2023	X	1:15	8:45 pm
Ahamed Careem	Final Dissertation	Collecting Surveys		Drafting Survey Questions	10/14/2023	X	3:00	7:00 pm
Ahamed Careem	Final Dissertation	Collecting Surveys		Drafting Survey Questions	10/15/2023	X	1:15	8:45 pm

Solent University - Dissertation Project Timesheet - Ahamed Careem

FROM 01/01/2016 TO 01/22/2024

Ahamed Careem	Final Dissertation	Collecting Surveys		Find and reach out to Target Audience	10/16/2023	X	1:30	4:00 am
Ahamed Careem	Final Dissertation	Collecting Surveys		Collecting Survey Results	10/16/2023	X	1:30	5:30 pm
Ahamed Careem	Final Dissertation	Collecting Surveys		Find and reach out to Target Audience (Send to Coworkers)	10/17/2023	X	1:40	10:00 am
Ahamed Careem	Final Dissertation	Collecting Surveys		Collecting Survey Results	10/17/2023	X	1:30	5:30 pm
Ahamed Careem	Final Dissertation	Collecting Surveys		Find and reach out to Target Audience (Send & Share via LinkedIn)	10/18/2023	X	1:30	4:00 am
Ahamed Careem	Final Dissertation	Collecting Surveys		Collecting Survey Results	10/18/2023	X	1:30	5:30 pm
Ahamed Careem	Final Dissertation	Collecting Surveys		Analyze Survey Results	10/19/2023	X	0:30	5:00 am
Ahamed Careem	Final Dissertation	Collecting Surveys		Collecting Survey Results	10/19/2023	X	1:30	5:30 pm
Ahamed Careem	Final Dissertation	Collecting Surveys		Analyze Survey Results	10/20/2023	X	0:30	5:00 am
Ahamed Careem	Final Dissertation	Collecting Surveys		Collecting Survey Results	10/20/2023	X	1:30	5:30 pm
Ahamed Careem	Final Dissertation	Collecting Surveys		Analyze Survey Results	10/21/2023	X	0:30	5:00 am
Ahamed Careem	Final Dissertation	Collecting Surveys		Collecting Survey Results	10/21/2023	X	1:30	5:30 pm
Ahamed Careem	Final Dissertation	Collecting Surveys		Analyze Survey Results	10/22/2023	X	0:30	5:00 am
Ahamed Careem	Final Dissertation	Collecting Surveys		Collecting Survey Results	10/22/2023	X	1:30	5:30 pm
Ahamed Careem	Final Dissertation	Collecting Surveys		Analyze Survey Results	10/23/2023	X	0:30	5:00 am
Ahamed Careem	Final Dissertation	Collecting Surveys		Checking for patterns and trends in survey results	10/27/2023	X	2:00	6:00 pm
Ahamed Careem	Final Dissertation	Collecting Surveys		Identifying various trends on the survey results and doing Research	10/28/2023	X	4:00	9:00 am
Ahamed Careem	Final Dissertation	Collecting Surveys		Documentation and Analysis based on survey	12/25/2023	X	4:00	9:00 am

TASK

Develop ML Model

DURATION

77:15

User	Project	Task	Client	Notes	Date	Billed	Duration	From
Ahamed Careem	Final Dissertation	Develop ML Model		Finding a Good Dataset for Model Training	10/19/2023	X	1:00	9:00 pm
Ahamed Careem	Final Dissertation	Develop ML Model		Finding a Good Dataset for Model Training	10/20/2023	X	1:00	9:00 pm
Ahamed Careem	Final Dissertation	Develop ML Model		Finding a Good Dataset for Model Training	10/21/2023	X	1:00	9:00 pm
Ahamed Careem	Final Dissertation	Develop ML Model		Finding a Good Dataset for Model Training	10/22/2023	X	1:00	9:00 pm
Ahamed Careem	Final Dissertation	Develop ML Model		Finding a Good Dataset for Model Training	10/23/2023	X	1:00	9:00 pm

Solent University - Dissertation Project Timesheet - Ahamed Careem

FROM 01/01/2016 TO 01/22/2024

Ahamed Careem	Final Dissertation	Develop ML Model		Finding a Good Dataset for Model Training	10/24/2023	X	1:30	4:30 am
Ahamed Careem	Final Dissertation	Develop ML Model		Analyzing, Identifying and Testing Datasets	10/24/2023	X	3:00	7:30 pm
Ahamed Careem	Final Dissertation	Develop ML Model		Analyzing, Identifying and Testing Datasets	10/25/2023	X	3:00	7:30 pm
Ahamed Careem	Final Dissertation	Develop ML Model		Finding a Good Dataset for Model Training	10/25/2023	X	1:00	9:00 pm
Ahamed Careem	Final Dissertation	Develop ML Model		Analyzing, Identifying and Testing Datasets	10/26/2023	X	3:00	7:30 pm
Ahamed Careem	Final Dissertation	Develop ML Model		Filtering out the better datasets	10/28/2023	X	5:00	7:30 pm
Ahamed Careem	Final Dissertation	Develop ML Model		Verifying the source and accuracy of selected datasets	10/29/2023	X	4:20	9:00 am
Ahamed Careem	Final Dissertation	Develop ML Model		Cleaning the datasets	11/04/2023	X	6:00	6:00 am
Ahamed Careem	Final Dissertation	Develop ML Model		Analyze dataset, check for missing values and fill them, check for unique values	11/05/2023	X	5:00	9:00 am
Ahamed Careem	Final Dissertation	Develop ML Model		Visualizing Dataset, Checking data types, Do Label Encoding, Split data into training and testing sets	11/05/2023	X	5:00	3:45 pm
Ahamed Careem	Final Dissertation	Develop ML Model		Choosing appropriate ML Techniques	11/06/2023	X	5:25	6:30 pm
Ahamed Careem	Final Dissertation	Develop ML Model		Initialize RandomForestClassifier LogisticRegression SVC KNeighborsClassifier GradientBoostingClassifier models	11/07/2023	X	4:00	7:00 pm
Ahamed Careem	Final Dissertation	Develop ML Model		Training the Model with Sample Data	11/10/2023	X	4:00	7:30 pm
Ahamed Careem	Final Dissertation	Develop ML Model		Training the Model with Sample Data	11/11/2023	X	4:00	7:30 pm
Ahamed Careem	Final Dissertation	Develop ML Model		Training the Model with Sample Data	11/12/2023	X	4:10	7:30 am
Ahamed Careem	Final Dissertation	Develop ML Model		Doing and testing various visualizations with data to analyze	11/13/2023	X	4:30	7:00 pm
Ahamed Careem	Final Dissertation	Develop ML Model		Prediction with Best Model	11/14/2023	X	4:20	7:15 pm
Ahamed Careem	Final Dissertation	Develop ML Model		Testing the model with various test cases	11/15/2023	X	5:00	6:30 pm
TASK							DURATION	
Documentation							47:40	
User	Project	Task	Client	Notes	Date	Billed	Duration	From
Ahamed Careem	Final Dissertation	Documentation		Documenting and Noting down various findings	11/16/2023	X	4:40	7:00 pm
Ahamed Careem	Final Dissertation	Documentation		Documentation and report writing	12/18/2023	X	3:00	7:00 pm
Ahamed Careem	Final Dissertation	Documentation		Documentation and report writing	12/19/2023	X	3:00	7:00 pm
Ahamed Careem	Final Dissertation	Documentation		Documentation and report writing	12/20/2023	X	3:00	7:00 pm
Ahamed Careem	Final Dissertation	Documentation		Documentation and report writing	12/21/2023	X	3:00	7:00 pm

Solent University - Dissertation Project Timesheet - Ahamed Careem

FROM 01/01/2016 TO 01/22/2024

Ahamed Careem	Final Dissertation	Documentation		Documentation and report writing	12/22/2023	X	3:00	7:00 pm
Ahamed Careem	Final Dissertation	Documentation		Documentation and report writing	12/23/2023	X	3:00	7:00 pm
Ahamed Careem	Final Dissertation	Documentation		Documentation and report writing	12/24/2023	X	3:00	7:00 pm
Ahamed Careem	Final Dissertation	Documentation		Documentation	01/06/2024	X	5:00	7:00 am
Ahamed Careem	Final Dissertation	Documentation		Documentation	01/07/2024	X	5:00	7:00 am
Ahamed Careem	Final Dissertation	Documentation		Documentation	01/08/2024	X	1:00	8:30 pm
Ahamed Careem	Final Dissertation	Documentation		Documentation	01/09/2024	X	1:00	8:30 pm
Ahamed Careem	Final Dissertation	Documentation		Documentation	01/10/2024	X	1:00	8:30 pm
Ahamed Careem	Final Dissertation	Documentation		Documentation	01/12/2024	X	1:00	8:30 pm
Ahamed Careem	Final Dissertation	Documentation		Documentation	01/13/2024	X	1:00	8:30 pm
Ahamed Careem	Final Dissertation	Documentation		Filling out the design requirement part	01/14/2024	X	1:00	8:30 pm
Ahamed Careem	Final Dissertation	Documentation		Create PowerPoint Slide	01/20/2024	X	3:00	9:00 am
Ahamed Careem	Final Dissertation	Documentation		Create PowerPoint Slide	01/21/2024	X	3:00	9:00 am

TASK

Frontend Coding

DURATION

143:40

User	Project	Task	Client	Notes	Date	Billed	Duration	From
Ahamed Careem	Final Dissertation	Frontend Coding		Looking into CV Generation part development	11/18/2023	X	4:00	10:00 am
Ahamed Careem	Final Dissertation	Frontend Coding		Choosing Frontend Layout	11/18/2023	X	6:00	4:00 pm
Ahamed Careem	Final Dissertation	Frontend Coding		Start frontend coding structure	11/19/2023	X	5:30	7:30 am
Ahamed Careem	Final Dissertation	Frontend Coding		Coding CV Template Structure	11/19/2023	X	5:00	3:00 pm
Ahamed Careem	Final Dissertation	Frontend Coding		Coding CV Template Structure	11/20/2023	X	5:45	6:00 pm
Ahamed Careem	Final Dissertation	Frontend Coding		Coding CV Template Structure	11/21/2023	X	4:05	7:00 pm
Ahamed Careem	Final Dissertation	Frontend Coding		Coding CV Template Structure	11/22/2023	X	5:00	6:00 pm
Ahamed Careem	Final Dissertation	Frontend Coding		About us Page coding	11/25/2023	X	2:30	6:00 am
Ahamed Careem	Final Dissertation	Frontend Coding		Design a Logo and other icons	11/25/2023	X	2:00	11:00 am
Ahamed Careem	Final Dissertation	Frontend Coding		Design CV Template page and Test them	11/25/2023	X	7:00	3:00 pm
Ahamed Careem	Final Dissertation	Frontend Coding		CV Template coding and error fixing	11/26/2023	X	5:50	7:10 am

Solent University - Dissertation Project Timesheet - Ahamed Careem

FROM 01/01/2016 TO 01/22/2024

Ahamed Careem	Final Dissertation	Frontend Coding	CV Template coding and error fixing	11/26/2023	X	6:00	2:00 pm
Ahamed Careem	Final Dissertation	Frontend Coding	Frontend Coding (Templates, Testing and Layouts)	11/27/2023	X	4:00	7:30 pm
Ahamed Careem	Final Dissertation	Frontend Coding	Frontend Coding (Templates, Testing and Layouts)	11/28/2023	X	4:00	7:30 pm
Ahamed Careem	Final Dissertation	Frontend Coding	Frontend Coding (Templates, Testing and Layouts)	11/29/2023	X	4:00	7:30 pm
Ahamed Careem	Final Dissertation	Frontend Coding	Frontend Coding (Templates, Testing and Layouts)	11/30/2023	X	4:00	7:30 pm
Ahamed Careem	Final Dissertation	Frontend Coding	Frontend Coding (Templates, Testing and Layouts)	12/01/2023	X	4:00	7:30 pm
Ahamed Careem	Final Dissertation	Frontend Coding	Create UI for Career prediction and Integrate with Backend	12/03/2023	X	7:00	6:00 am
Ahamed Careem	Final Dissertation	Frontend Coding	FrontEnd Coding	12/04/2023	X	3:00	6:30 pm
Ahamed Careem	Final Dissertation	Frontend Coding	FrontEnd Coding	12/05/2023	X	3:00	6:30 pm
Ahamed Careem	Final Dissertation	Frontend Coding	FrontEnd Coding	12/06/2023	X	3:00	6:30 pm
Ahamed Careem	Final Dissertation	Frontend Coding	FrontEnd Coding	12/07/2023	X	3:00	6:30 pm
Ahamed Careem	Final Dissertation	Frontend Coding	FrontEnd Coding	12/08/2023	X	3:00	6:30 pm
Ahamed Careem	Final Dissertation	Frontend Coding	FrontEnd Coding	12/09/2023	X	3:00	6:30 pm
Ahamed Careem	Final Dissertation	Frontend Coding	FrontEnd Coding	12/10/2023	X	3:00	6:30 pm
Ahamed Careem	Final Dissertation	Frontend Coding	FrontEnd Coding	12/11/2023	X	3:00	6:30 pm
Ahamed Careem	Final Dissertation	Frontend Coding	FrontEnd Coding	12/12/2023	X	3:00	6:30 pm
Ahamed Careem	Final Dissertation	Frontend Coding	FrontEnd Coding	12/13/2023	X	3:00	6:30 pm
Ahamed Careem	Final Dissertation	Frontend Coding	FrontEnd Coding	12/14/2023	X	3:00	6:30 pm
Ahamed Careem	Final Dissertation	Frontend Coding	FrontEnd Coding	12/15/2023	X	3:00	6:30 pm
Ahamed Careem	Final Dissertation	Frontend Coding	FrontEnd Coding	12/16/2023	X	3:00	6:30 pm
Ahamed Careem	Final Dissertation	Frontend Coding	FrontEnd Coding	12/17/2023	X	3:00	6:30 pm
Ahamed Careem	Final Dissertation	Frontend Coding	Code the AI Suggestion feature	12/27/2023	X	2:00	5:00 am
Ahamed Careem	Final Dissertation	Frontend Coding	Code the AI Suggestion feature	12/28/2023	X	2:00	5:00 am
Ahamed Careem	Final Dissertation	Frontend Coding	Code the AI Suggestion feature	12/29/2023	X	2:00	5:00 am
Ahamed Careem	Final Dissertation	Frontend Coding	Create UI for Career advising, Skills advising and Qualification advising	12/31/2023	X	5:30	7:00 am

Solent University - Dissertation Project Timesheet - Ahamed Careem

FROM 01/01/2016 TO 01/22/2024

Ahamed Careem	Final Dissertation	Frontend Coding		Create the Mock Interview Feature	01/15/2024	X	2:40	9:00 am
Ahamed Careem	Final Dissertation	Frontend Coding		Final Tweaks	01/18/2024	X	1:50	10:00 pm
TASK							DURATION	
Learning/Improving Skill							5:00	
User	Project	Task	Client	Notes	Date	Billed	Duration	From
Ahamed Careem	Final Dissertation	Learning/Improving Skill		Learning and Improving ML skill	10/30/2023	X	1:00	9:00 pm
Ahamed Careem	Final Dissertation	Learning/Improving Skill		Learning and Improving ML skill	10/31/2023	X	1:00	9:00 pm
Ahamed Careem	Final Dissertation	Learning/Improving Skill		Learning and Improving ML skill	11/01/2023	X	1:00	9:00 pm
Ahamed Careem	Final Dissertation	Learning/Improving Skill		Learning and Improving ML skill	11/02/2023	X	1:00	9:00 pm
Ahamed Careem	Final Dissertation	Learning/Improving Skill		Learning and Improving ML skill	11/03/2023	X	1:00	9:00 pm
TASK							DURATION	
Literature Review							13:30	
User	Project	Task	Client	Notes	Date	Billed	Duration	From
Ahamed Careem	Final Dissertation	Literature Review		Searching and drafting literature review	10/02/2023	X	1:30	9:30 pm
Ahamed Careem	Final Dissertation	Literature Review		Searching and drafting literature review	10/03/2023	X	1:30	9:30 pm
Ahamed Careem	Final Dissertation	Literature Review		Searching and drafting literature review	10/04/2023	X	1:30	9:30 pm
Ahamed Careem	Final Dissertation	Literature Review		Searching and drafting literature review	10/05/2023	X	1:30	9:30 pm
Ahamed Careem	Final Dissertation	Literature Review		Searching and drafting literature review	10/07/2023	X	1:30	9:30 pm
Ahamed Careem	Final Dissertation	Literature Review		Writing Literature review and more research	10/22/2023	X	4:00	9:00 am
Ahamed Careem	Final Dissertation	Literature Review		Continuing Literature review	10/29/2023	X	2:00	5:00 pm
TASK							DURATION	
Project Proposal							13:50	
User	Project	Task	Client	Notes	Date	Billed	Duration	From
Ahamed Careem	Final Dissertation	Project Proposal		Starting to work on Project Online	09/05/2023	X	4:00	7:00 pm
Ahamed Careem	Final Dissertation	Project Proposal		Drafting Project Proposal	09/06/2023	X	2:00	9:30 pm
Ahamed Careem	Final Dissertation	Project Proposal		Drafting Project Proposal	09/07/2023	X	2:00	9:30 pm
Ahamed Careem	Final Dissertation	Project Proposal		Drafting Project Proposal	09/09/2023	X	2:00	9:30 pm
Ahamed Careem	Final Dissertation	Project Proposal		Drafting Project Proposal	09/11/2023	X	2:00	9:30 pm
Ahamed Careem	Final Dissertation	Project Proposal		Project proposal review	09/16/2023	X	1:50	10:30 pm

Solent University - Dissertation Project Timesheet - Ahamed Careem

FROM 01/01/2016 TO 01/22/2024

TASK								DURATION
Research & Development								32:10
User	Project	Task	Client	Notes	Date	Billed	Duration	From
Ahamed Careem	Final Dissertation	Research & Development		Doing Research Regarding the Project	09/01/2023	X	5:00	3:00 pm
Ahamed Careem	Final Dissertation	Research & Development		Improving Python skills to develop ML	09/30/2023	X	3:00	7:00 pm
Ahamed Careem	Final Dissertation	Research & Development		Understanding AI in CV creation & career guidance:	10/08/2023	X	4:00	2:30 pm
Ahamed Careem	Final Dissertation	Research & Development		Understanding AI in CV creation & career guidance:	10/10/2023	X	3:00	6:30 pm
Ahamed Careem	Final Dissertation	Research & Development		Studying the existing market solutions	10/12/2023	X	2:00	8:30 pm
Ahamed Careem	Final Dissertation	Research & Development		Studying the existing market solutions	10/13/2023	X	1:45	10:00 pm
Ahamed Careem	Final Dissertation	Research & Development		Studying the existing market solutions	10/14/2023	X	2:00	6:00 am
Ahamed Careem	Final Dissertation	Research & Development		Doing R&D on Existing Marketing Solutions	10/14/2023	X	2:00	4:00 pm
Ahamed Careem	Final Dissertation	Research & Development		Studying the existing market solutions	10/15/2023	X	3:10	8:00 am
Ahamed Careem	Final Dissertation	Research & Development		Doing R&D on Existing Marketing Solutions	10/15/2023	X	2:00	4:00 pm
Ahamed Careem	Final Dissertation	Research & Development		Doing R&D on existing market solutions	10/16/2023	X	2:15	9:15 pm
Ahamed Careem	Final Dissertation	Research & Development		Doing research on whats the most suitable model to use	11/12/2023	X	2:00	7:30 pm
TASK								DURATION
Testing								18:00
User	Project	Task	Client	Notes	Date	Billed	Duration	From
Ahamed Careem	Final Dissertation	Testing		App Testing	12/09/2023	X	3:30	6:00 am
Ahamed Careem	Final Dissertation	Testing		App Testing	12/10/2023	X	3:30	6:00 am
Ahamed Careem	Final Dissertation	Testing		Testing the app and fixing issues	12/26/2023	X	3:00	8:00 pm
Ahamed Careem	Final Dissertation	Testing		Testing the app and fixing issues	12/27/2023	X	3:00	8:00 pm
Ahamed Careem	Final Dissertation	Testing		Testing the app and fixing issues	12/28/2023	X	3:00	8:00 pm
Ahamed Careem	Final Dissertation	Testing		Finalized Testing	01/19/2024	X	2:00	8:00 pm

BILLED / WORK TIME

0:00 / 414:45

DAILY TIME SHEET ENTRY

Task	Notes	Date	Duration	Hours	From	To
Research & Development	Doing Research Regarding the Project	09-01-2023	5:00:00	5	3:00 pm	8:00 pm
Project Proposal	Starting to work on Project Online	09-05-2023	4:00:00	4	7:00 pm	11:00 pm
Project Proposal	Drafting Project Proposal	09-06-2023	2:00:00	2	9:30 pm	11:30 pm
Project Proposal	Drafting Project Proposal	09-07-2023	2:00:00	2	9:30 pm	11:30 pm
Project Proposal	Drafting Project Proposal	09-09-2023	2:00:00	2	9:30 pm	11:30 pm
Project Proposal	Drafting Project Proposal	09-11-2023	2:00:00	2	9:30 pm	11:30 pm
Project Proposal	Project proposal review	09-16-2023	1:50:00	1.83	10:30 pm	12:20 am
Research & Development	Improving Python skills to develop ML	09-30-2023	3:00:00	3	7:00 pm	10:00 pm
Literature Review	Searching and drafting literature review	10-02-2023	1:30:00	1.5	9:30 pm	11:00 pm
Literature Review	Searching and drafting literature review	10-03-2023	1:30:00	1.5	9:30 pm	11:00 pm
Literature Review	Searching and drafting literature review	10-04-2023	1:30:00	1.5	9:30 pm	11:00 pm
Literature Review	Searching and drafting literature review	10-05-2023	1:30:00	1.5	9:30 pm	11:00 pm
Literature Review	Searching and drafting literature review	10-07-2023	1:30:00	1.5	9:30 pm	11:00 pm
Research & Development	Understanding AI in CV creation & career guidance:	10-08-2023	4:00:00	4	2:30 pm	6:30 pm
Research & Development	Understanding AI in CV creation & career guidance:	10-10-2023	3:00:00	3	6:30 pm	9:30 pm
Research & Development	Studying the existing market solutions	10-12-2023	2:00:00	2	8:30 pm	10:30 pm
Collecting Surveys	Drafting Survey Questions	10-13-2023	1:15:00	1.25	8:45 pm	10:00 pm
Research & Development	Studying the existing market solutions	10-13-2023	1:45:00	1.75	10:00 pm	11:45 pm
Research & Development	Studying the existing market solutions	10-14-2023	2:00:00	2	6:00 am	8:00 am
Research & Development	Doing R&D on Existing Marketing Solutions	10-14-2023	2:00:00	2	4:00 pm	6:00 pm
Collecting Surveys	Drafting Survey Questions	10-14-2023	3:00:00	3	7:00 pm	10:00 pm
Research & Development	Studying the existing market solutions	10-15-2023	3:10:00	3.17	8:00 am	11:10 am
Research & Development	Doing R&D on Existing Marketing Solutions	10-15-2023	2:00:00	2	4:00 pm	6:00 pm
Collecting Surveys	Drafting Survey Questions	10-15-2023	1:15:00	1.25	8:45 pm	10:00 pm

Collecting Surveys	Find and reach out to Target Audience	10-16-2023	1:30:00	1.5	4:00 am	5:30 am
Collecting Surveys	Collecting Survey Results	10-16-2023	1:30:00	1.5	5:30 pm	7:00 pm
Research & Development	Doing R&D on existing market solutions	10-16-2023	2:15:00	2.25	9:15 pm	11:30 pm
Collecting Surveys	Find and reach out to Target Audience (Send to Coworkers)	10-17-2023	1:40:00	1.67	10:00 am	11:40 am
Collecting Surveys	Collecting Survey Results	10-17-2023	1:30:00	1.5	5:30 pm	7:00 pm
Collecting Surveys	Find and reach out to Target Audience (Send & Share via LinkedIn)	10-18-2023	1:30:00	1.5	4:00 am	5:30 am
Collecting Surveys	Collecting Survey Results	10-18-2023	1:30:00	1.5	5:30 pm	7:00 pm
Collecting Surveys	Analyze Survey Results	10-19-2023	0:30:00	0.5	5:00 am	5:30 am
Collecting Surveys	Collecting Survey Results	10-19-2023	1:30:00	1.5	5:30 pm	7:00 pm
Develop ML Model	Finding a Good Dataset for Model Training	10-19-2023	1:00:00	1	9:00 pm	10:00 pm
Collecting Surveys	Analyze Survey Results	10-20-2023	0:30:00	0.5	5:00 am	5:30 am
Collecting Surveys	Collecting Survey Results	10-20-2023	1:30:00	1.5	5:30 pm	7:00 pm
Develop ML Model	Finding a Good Dataset for Model Training	10-20-2023	1:00:00	1	9:00 pm	10:00 pm
Collecting Surveys	Analyze Survey Results	10-21-2023	0:30:00	0.5	5:00 am	5:30 am
Collecting Surveys	Collecting Survey Results	10-21-2023	1:30:00	1.5	5:30 pm	7:00 pm
Develop ML Model	Finding a Good Dataset for Model Training	10-21-2023	1:00:00	1	9:00 pm	10:00 pm
Collecting Surveys	Analyze Survey Results	10-22-2023	0:30:00	0.5	5:00 am	5:30 am
Literature Review	Writing Literature review and more research	10-22-2023	4:00:00	4	9:00 am	1:00 pm
Collecting Surveys	Collecting Survey Results	10-22-2023	1:30:00	1.5	5:30 pm	7:00 pm
Develop ML Model	Finding a Good Dataset for Model Training	10-22-2023	1:00:00	1	9:00 pm	10:00 pm
Collecting Surveys	Analyze Survey Results	10-23-2023	0:30:00	0.5	5:00 am	5:30 am
Develop ML Model	Finding a Good Dataset for Model Training	10-23-2023	1:00:00	1	9:00 pm	10:00 pm
Develop ML Model	Finding a Good Dataset for Model Training	10-24-2023	1:30:00	1.5	4:30 am	6:00 am
Develop ML Model	Analyzing, Identifying and Testing Datasets	10-24-2023	3:00:00	3	7:30 pm	10:30 pm
Develop ML Model	Analyzing, Identifying and Testing Datasets	10-25-2023	3:00:00	3	7:30 pm	10:30 pm

Develop ML Model	Finding a Good Dataset for Model Training	10-25-2023	1:00:00	1	9:00 pm	10:00 pm
Develop ML Model	Analyzing, Identifying and Testing Datasets	10-26-2023	3:00:00	3	7:30 pm	10:30 pm
Collecting Surveys	Checking for patterns and trends in survey results	10-27-2023	2:00:00	2	6:00 pm	8:00 pm
Collecting Surveys	Identifying various trends on the survey results and doing Research	10-28-2023	4:00:00	4	9:00 am	1:00 pm
Develop ML Model	Filtering out the better datasets	10-28-2023	5:00:00	5	7:30 pm	12:30 am
Develop ML Model	Verifying the source and accuracy of selected datasets	10-29-2023	4:20:00	4.33	9:00 am	1:20 pm
Literature Review	Continuing Literature review	10-29-2023	2:00:00	2	5:00 pm	7:00 pm
Learning/Improving Skill	Learning and Improving ML skill	10-30-2023	1:00:00	1	9:00 pm	10:00 pm
Learning/Improving Skill	Learning and Improving ML skill	10-31-2023	1:00:00	1	9:00 pm	10:00 pm
Learning/Improving Skill	Learning and Improving ML skill	11-01-2023	1:00:00	1	9:00 pm	10:00 pm
Learning/Improving Skill	Learning and Improving ML skill	11-02-2023	1:00:00	1	9:00 pm	10:00 pm
Learning/Improving Skill	Learning and Improving ML skill	11-03-2023	1:00:00	1	9:00 pm	10:00 pm
Develop ML Model	Cleaning the datasets	11-04-2023	6:00:00	6	6:00 am	12:00 pm
Develop ML Model	Analyze dataset, check for missing values and fill them, check for unique values	11-05-2023	5:00:00	5	9:00 am	2:00 pm
Develop ML Model	Visualizing Dataset, Checking data types, Do Label Encoding, Split data into training and testing sets	11-05-2023	5:00:00	5	3:45 pm	8:45 pm
Develop ML Model	Choosing appropriate ML Techniques	11-06-2023	5:25:00	5.42	6:30 pm	11:55 pm
Develop ML Model	Initialize RandomForestClassifier LogisticRegression SVC KNeighborsClassifier GradientBoostingClassifier models	11-07-2023	4:00:00	4	7:00 pm	11:00 pm
Develop ML Model	Training the Model with Sample Data	11-10-2023	4:00:00	4	7:30 pm	11:30 pm
Develop ML Model	Training the Model with Sample Data	11-11-2023	4:00:00	4	7:30 pm	11:30 pm
Develop ML Model	Training the Model with Sample Data	11-12-2023	4:10:00	4.17	7:30 am	11:40 am
Research & Development	Doing research on what the most suitable model to use	11-12-2023	2:00:00	2	7:30 pm	9:30 pm
Develop ML Model	Doing and testing various visualizations with data to analyze	11-13-2023	4:30:00	4.5	7:00 pm	11:30 pm

Develop ML Model	Prediction with Best Model	11-14-2023	4:20:00	4.33	7:15 pm	11:35 pm
Develop ML Model	Testing the model with various test cases	11-15-2023	5:00:00	5	6:30 pm	11:30 pm
Documentation	Documenting and Noting down various findings	11-16-2023	4:40:00	4.67	7:00 pm	11:40 pm
Frontend Coding	Looking into CV Generation part development	11-18-2023	4:00:00	4	10:00 am	2:00 pm
Frontend Coding	Choosing Frontend Layout	11-18-2023	6:00:00	6	4:00 pm	10:00 pm
Frontend Coding	Start frontend coding structure	11-19-2023	5:30:00	5.5	7:30 am	1:00 pm
Frontend Coding	Coding CV Template Structure	11-19-2023	5:00:00	5	3:00 pm	8:00 pm
Frontend Coding	Coding CV Template Structure	11-20-2023	5:45:00	5.75	6:00 pm	11:45 pm
Frontend Coding	Coding CV Template Structure	11-21-2023	4:05:00	4.08	7:00 pm	11:05 pm
Frontend Coding	Coding CV Template Structure	11-22-2023	5:00:00	5	6:00 pm	11:00 pm
Frontend Coding	About us Page coding	11-25-2023	2:30:00	2.5	6:00 am	8:30 am
Frontend Coding	Design a Logo and other icons	11-25-2023	2:00:00	2	11:00 am	1:00 pm
Frontend Coding	Design CV Template page and Test them	11-25-2023	7:00:00	7	3:00 pm	10:00 pm
Frontend Coding	CV Template coding and error fixing	11-26-2023	5:50:00	5.83	7:10 am	1:00 pm
Frontend Coding	CV Template coding and error fixing	11-26-2023	6:00:00	6	2:00 pm	8:00 pm
Frontend Coding	Frontend Coding (Templates, Testing and Layouts)	11-27-2023	4:00:00	4	7:30 pm	11:30 pm
Frontend Coding	Frontend Coding (Templates, Testing and Layouts)	11-28-2023	4:00:00	4	7:30 pm	11:30 pm
Frontend Coding	Frontend Coding (Templates, Testing and Layouts)	11-29-2023	4:00:00	4	7:30 pm	11:30 pm
Frontend Coding	Frontend Coding (Templates, Testing and Layouts)	11-30-2023	4:00:00	4	7:30 pm	11:30 pm
Frontend Coding	Frontend Coding (Templates, Testing and Layouts)	12-01-2023	4:00:00	4	7:30 pm	11:30 pm
Backend Coding	Testing model, exporting model and adding to Backend	12-02-2023	7:00:00	7	6:00 am	1:00 pm
Frontend Coding	Create UI for Career prediction and Integrate with Backend	12-03-2023	7:00:00	7	6:00 am	1:00 pm
Frontend Coding	FrontEnd Coding	12-04-2023	3:00:00	3	6:30 pm	9:30 pm
Backend Coding	Back End Coding	12-04-2023	1:00:00	1	9:30 pm	10:30 pm
Frontend Coding	FrontEnd Coding	12-05-2023	3:00:00	3	6:30 pm	9:30 pm

Backend Coding	Back End Coding	12-05-2023	1:00:00	1	9:30 pm	10:30 pm
Frontend Coding	FrontEnd Coding	12-06-2023	3:00:00	3	6:30 pm	9:30 pm
Backend Coding	Back End Coding	12-06-2023	1:00:00	1	9:30 pm	10:30 pm
Frontend Coding	FrontEnd Coding	12-07-2023	3:00:00	3	6:30 pm	9:30 pm
Backend Coding	Back End Coding	12-07-2023	1:00:00	1	9:30 pm	10:30 pm
Frontend Coding	FrontEnd Coding	12-08-2023	3:00:00	3	6:30 pm	9:30 pm
Backend Coding	Back End Coding	12-08-2023	1:00:00	1	9:30 pm	10:30 pm
Testing	App Testing	12-09-2023	3:30:00	3.5	6:00 am	9:30 am
Frontend Coding	FrontEnd Coding	12-09-2023	3:00:00	3	6:30 pm	9:30 pm
Backend Coding	Back End Coding	12-09-2023	1:00:00	1	9:30 pm	10:30 pm
Testing	App Testing	12-10-2023	3:30:00	3.5	6:00 am	9:30 am
Frontend Coding	FrontEnd Coding	12-10-2023	3:00:00	3	6:30 pm	9:30 pm
Backend Coding	Back End Coding	12-10-2023	1:00:00	1	9:30 pm	10:30 pm
Frontend Coding	FrontEnd Coding	12-11-2023	3:00:00	3	6:30 pm	9:30 pm
Backend Coding	Back End Coding	12-11-2023	1:00:00	1	9:30 pm	10:30 pm
Frontend Coding	FrontEnd Coding	12-12-2023	3:00:00	3	6:30 pm	9:30 pm
Backend Coding	Back End Coding	12-12-2023	1:00:00	1	9:30 pm	10:30 pm
Frontend Coding	FrontEnd Coding	12-13-2023	3:00:00	3	6:30 pm	9:30 pm
Backend Coding	Back End Coding	12-13-2023	1:00:00	1	9:30 pm	10:30 pm
Frontend Coding	FrontEnd Coding	12-14-2023	3:00:00	3	6:30 pm	9:30 pm
Backend Coding	Back End Coding	12-14-2023	1:00:00	1	9:30 pm	10:30 pm
Frontend Coding	FrontEnd Coding	12-15-2023	3:00:00	3	6:30 pm	9:30 pm
Backend Coding	Back End Coding	12-15-2023	1:00:00	1	9:30 pm	10:30 pm
Frontend Coding	FrontEnd Coding	12-16-2023	3:00:00	3	6:30 pm	9:30 pm
Backend Coding	Back End Coding	12-16-2023	1:00:00	1	9:30 pm	10:30 pm

Frontend Coding	FrontEnd Coding	12-17-2023	3:00:00	3	6:30 pm	9:30 pm
Backend Coding	Back End Coding	12-17-2023	1:00:00	1	9:30 pm	10:30 pm
Documentation	Documentation and report writing	12-18-2023	3:00:00	3	7:00 pm	10:00 pm
Documentation	Documentation and report writing	12-19-2023	3:00:00	3	7:00 pm	10:00 pm
Documentation	Documentation and report writing	12-20-2023	3:00:00	3	7:00 pm	10:00 pm
Documentation	Documentation and report writing	12-21-2023	3:00:00	3	7:00 pm	10:00 pm
Documentation	Documentation and report writing	12-22-2023	3:00:00	3	7:00 pm	10:00 pm
Documentation	Documentation and report writing	12-23-2023	3:00:00	3	7:00 pm	10:00 pm
Documentation	Documentation and report writing	12-24-2023	3:00:00	3	7:00 pm	10:00 pm
Collecting Surveys	Documentation and Analysis based on survey	12-25-2023	4:00:00	4	9:00 am	1:00 pm
Testing	Testing the app and fixing issues	12-26-2023	3:00:00	3	8:00 pm	11:00 pm
Frontend Coding	Code the AI Suggestion feature	12-27-2023	2:00:00	2	5:00 am	7:00 am
Testing	Testing the app and fixing issues	12-27-2023	3:00:00	3	8:00 pm	11:00 pm
Frontend Coding	Code the AI Suggestion feature	12-28-2023	2:00:00	2	5:00 am	7:00 am
Testing	Testing the app and fixing issues	12-28-2023	3:00:00	3	8:00 pm	11:00 pm
Frontend Coding	Code the AI Suggestion feature	12-29-2023	2:00:00	2	5:00 am	7:00 am
Backend Coding	Integrate Career Advice, Qualification and Skills using AI	12-30-2023	8:00:00	8	6:00 am	2:00 pm
Frontend Coding	Create UI for Career advising, Skills advising and Qualification advising	12-31-2023	5:30:00	5.5	7:00 am	12:30 pm
Documentation	Documentation	01-06-2024	5:00:00	5	7:00 am	12:00 pm
Documentation	Documentation	01-07-2024	5:00:00	5	7:00 am	12:00 pm
Documentation	Documentation	01-08-2024	1:00:00	1	8:30 pm	9:30 pm
Documentation	Documentation	01-09-2024	1:00:00	1	8:30 pm	9:30 pm
Documentation	Documentation	01-10-2024	1:00:00	1	8:30 pm	9:30 pm
Documentation	Documentation	01-12-2024	1:00:00	1	8:30 pm	9:30 pm
Documentation	Documentation	01-13-2024	1:00:00	1	8:30 pm	9:30 pm

Documentation	Filling out the design requirement part	01-14-2024	1:00:00	1	8:30 pm	9:30 pm
Frontend Coding	Create the Mock Interview Feature	01-15-2024	2:40:00	2.67	9:00 am	11:40 am
Backend Coding	Final Tweaks	01-17-2024	1:30:00	1.5	5:00 am	6:30 am
Frontend Coding	Final Tweaks	01-18-2024	1:50:00	1.83	10:00 pm	11:50 pm
Testing	Finalized Testing	01-19-2024	2:00:00	2	8:00 pm	10:00 pm
Documentation	Create PowerPoint Slide	01-20-2024	3:00:00	3	9:00 am	12:00 pm
Documentation	Create PowerPoint Slide	01-21-2024	3:00:00	3	9:00 am	12:00 pm

Logbook

This is the Log Book maintained during the project

Week Starting	Activities	Barriers Encountered	Mitigation and Action Plans
Sep 04, 2023	Conducted initial research on AI technologies and existing CV generation tools. Began defining project scope and objectives.	Uncertainty about selecting the right ML model.	Conducted a comparative study of different ML models and consulted with a mentor.
Sep 11, 2023	Drafted project proposal, outlining goals, methodologies, and expected outcomes. Began literature review on machine learning applications in career guidance.	Difficulty articulating technical concepts in the proposal.	Sought peer reviews and utilized online resources to clarify technical writing.
Sep 18, 2023	Continued refining project proposal. Expanded literature review to include AI-driven recommendation systems.	Time management issues balancing research and proposal writing.	Implemented a strict schedule and prioritized tasks.
Sep 25, 2023	[No recorded activity due to personal commitments]	N/A	N/A
Oct 02, 2023	Resumed research focusing on different AI frameworks suitable for the project. Initiated detailed planning for the development phase.	Overwhelmed by the volume of relevant literature.	Focused on key sources and created a literature matrix for organization.
Oct 09, 2023	Began prototyping the initial version of the CV generator. Set up development environment and tools.	Technical issues with the development environment setup.	Sought assistance from online communities and other resources.
Oct 16, 2023	Started building the machine learning model for career prediction. Worked on data collection and preprocessing.		
Oct 23, 2023	Designed the initial layout of the frontend interface. Conducted usability tests with mockups.	Designing a user-friendly interface was more complex than anticipated.	Dedicated more time for Frontend

Week Starting	Activities	Barriers Encountered	Mitigation and Action Plans
Oct 30, 2023	Integrated the frontend with the backend. Began integration testing to ensure seamless connectivity.		
Nov 06, 2023	Conducted initial user testing of the prototype. Collected feedback for improvements.		
Nov 13, 2023	Implemented iterative improvements based on user feedback. Enhanced ML model accuracy.	Balancing between feature improvements and new developments.	Prioritized features based on user feedback and project goals.
Nov 20, 2023	Developed additional features, including a mock interview module. Updated system documentation.	Time constraints in implementing new features.	Focused on the most impactful features and planned for future updates.
Nov 27, 2023	Optimized system performance. Conducted load testing and fine-tuned the backend for efficiency.		
Dec 04, 2023	Completed comprehensive documentation and user guides. Began preparing for system deployment.	Difficulty in simplifying technical jargon for documentation.	Consulted documentation guidelines
Dec 11, 2023	Finalized system testing. Prepared for deployment by setting up a monitoring system.	Stress and anxiety about the upcoming deployment.	Implemented stress-reduction strategies and took a small break
Dec 18, 2023	Deployed the system. Monitored initial user interactions and system performance.		
Dec 25, 2023	Monitored user feedback post-launch. Provided user support and addressed queries.		
Jan 01, 2024	Analyzed user feedback and usage data. Began planning for future updates and feature additions.		

Week Starting	Activities	Barriers Encountered	Mitigation and Action Plans
Jan 08, 2024	Initiated development of new features based and updating the document		
Jan 15, 2024	Continued with more documentation on the report, Began testing and integrating these features into the existing system.		
Jan 22, 2024	Created PowerPoint slide, Focused on continuous improvement and refinement of the system. Evaluated user feedback for the recent updates.		